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Newton's Law of Gravitation and General Covariance

Research article

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Abstract**BACKGROUND:**

Newton's law of gravitation has long served as a foundational element in classical mechanics, describing the gravitational force as a scalar field. However, the traditional formulation lacks compatibility with the principles of general covariance inherent in modern physics.

MATERIAL AND METHODS:

By employing the language of differential geometry, we reformulate Newton's law of gravitation in a generally covariant form using the metric tensor. This approach allows for the exploration of gravitational phenomena within a framework that is consistent with general relativity.

RESULTS:

This investigation demonstrates that Newton's law of gravitation can be successfully expressed in a generally covariant form, opening up new avenues for theoretical exploration. Notably, this reformulation provides especially insights into the study of exotic gravitational structures, such as wormholes, and enhances our understanding of spacetime under extreme conditions.

CONCLUSION:

The generally covariant, n^{th} index, D -dimensional Newton's law of gravitation reveals new theoretical perspectives and potential applications, particularly in the study of non-trivial topologies in spacetime, offering a deeper comprehension of gravitational phenomena under a wider range of conditions.

Keywords:

Gravitation; Newton; Einstein; Relativity; Cause; Effect; Causal relationship k; Causality; Causation

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1. Introduction

Newton's law of gravitation, first published in 1687 in the *Philosophiæ Naturalis Principia Mathematica*, provided a simple scalar description of the gravitational force. Newton's law of gravitation states in its simple classical scalar form that the gravitational force F_R between two point masses m_{1R} and m_{2R} from the point of view of a relativistic observer is given by:

$$F_R = G_R \times \frac{m_{1R} \times m_{2R}}{d_R^2} \quad (1)$$

(see [Newton, 1687](#), pp.)

where:

- G_R is the gravitational constant from the point of view the relativistic observer,
- m_{1R} is the mass 1 from the point of view of a relativistic observer,
- m_{2R} is the mass 2 from the point of view of a relativistic observer,
- d_R is the distance between the two masses from the point of view of a relativistic observer.

and successfully explained the motion of planets and other astronomical phenomena for long time. However, its classical formulation inherently lacks the framework to address gravitational interactions in a manner that is consistent with the principles of modern physics, particularly the principle of general covariance. Nonetheless, it is purely a theoretical exercise to express something very simple in a mathematically complex way. While it is often useful to employ complex mathematical expressions for a more precise representation of certain aspects of objective reality, this does not change the logical validity of the underlying original simple theorem, assumed that the same is valid as such. A complicated mathematical expression of something very simple cannot logically invalidate the correctness of the simple one. Rather, mathematics should enhance clarity and precision without altering the fundamental characteristics of a simpler concept, assumed that the same is valid as such. In general, it is crucial to maintain a balance between mathematical complexity and conceptual clarity to better cope with processes of objective reality. In fact, expressing Newtonian gravity in a generally covariant form might be challenging and requiring differential geometry in its extended form. In other words, Newton's law of gravitation in a generally covariant form—one that remains valid under arbitrary coordinate transformations— will require at least the introduction of the metric tensor of general relativity $g_{\mu\nu}$, a mathematical construct that encapsulates the geometric and dynamic properties of spacetime. By incorporating the metric tensor of general relativity $g_{\mu\nu}$ into Newtonian gravity, we should align Newtonian gravity more closely with the relativistic framework introduced by Einstein. However, the Einstein field equations (EFE) describe the fundamental interaction of gravitation as a

result of spacetime being curved by matter and energy in a quite different from and at first glance does not have much in common with Newton's law of gravitation. The left-hand side of the Einstein field equations encapsulates the geometric properties of spacetime, while the right-hand side relates these to the matter and energy content of the universe. These equations are given as:

$$G_{\mu\nu} + (\Lambda \times g_{\mu\nu}) = \left(\frac{8 \times \pi \times G}{c^4} \right) \times T_{\mu\nu} \quad (2)$$

(see [Einstein, 1916](#), pp. 769–822)

where:

- $G_{\mu\nu}$ is the Einstein tensor, representing the curvature of spacetime.
- Λ is the cosmological constant, which accounts for the energy density of empty space, or "dark energy."
- $g_{\mu\nu}$ is the metric tensor, describing the geometry of spacetime.
- $T_{\mu\nu}$ is the stress-energy tensor, representing the distribution and flow of energy and momentum in spacetime.
- G is the gravitational constant, a fundamental physical constant describing the strength of gravity.
- c is the speed of light in a vacuum, a universal physical constant.

Potential Advantages

The theoretical motivation for seeking a generally covariant form of Newton's law lies in the quest for a unified description of physical phenomena. General covariance, a cornerstone of Einstein's theory of general relativity, posits that the laws of physics should take the same form in all coordinate systems. By casting Newtonian gravity within such a framework, we might be able to explore new conceptual pathways that could bridge the gap between classical and modern physics. This exercise not only might enhance the theoretical toolkit but also prompts authors to reevaluate the foundational assumptions underlying gravitational theory. Another and very important advantage of reformulating Newton's law in a generally covariant form is the potential to gain new insights into the nature of gravitational interactions. By employing the metric tensor of general relativity $g_{\mu\nu}$, we introduce a more comprehensive mathematical language capable of describing the geometry of spacetime and the influence of gravitational fields on matter. This approach may also provide a smoother conceptual transition from Newtonian gravity to general relativity, facilitating a deeper understanding of the relativistic effects that become significant in strong gravitational fields or at relativistic velocities.

Potential Dangers

Despite the theoretically very enticing prospects, a reformulation of Newton's law of gravitation in a generally covariant form is not without its theoretical dangers. Introducing general covariance into a fundamentally classical theory may lead to mathematical complexities and interpretational challenges. The risk of overcomplicating a well-understood theory must be carefully weighed against the potential benefits. Moreover, by extending the theory's framework, we may inadvertently introduce inconsistencies or discrepancies with experimental observations that have been well-explained by the original formulation. At the end, whether a reformulation of Newton's law of gravitation in a generally covariant while using the metric tensor of general relativity $g_{\mu\nu}$ might yield any significant theoretical insights or practical benefits, or any implications for our understanding of gravitational interactions, may be discussed later.

In general, the trial to formulate Newton's law of gravitation in a generally covariant form while using the metric tensor of general relativity $g_{\mu\nu}$ presents both intriguing possibilities and significant challenges. This paper will provide arguments, that such a manoeuvre makes theoretical and practical sense, evaluating its implications for the future of gravitational physics. By exploring this new terrain, we seek to deepen the understanding of gravity and its role in the broader context of the physics and cosmology.

2. Material and methods

2.1. Material

Co-moving observer 0

A co-moving observer 0 is an observer who is moving along with the reference frame of a system or entity under study in such a way that the same observer is at rest relative to such a frame of reference. This observer's frame of reference moves with the same velocity as the object being observed, meaning there is no relative motion between the observer and the object. In other words, the relative velocity, denoted as v , between the object being observed and the observer is $v = 0$. In such a frame of reference there are no distortions caused by relative motion and time dilation and length contraction effects et cetera do not apply to the object being observed, making it a fundamental concept in relativity and various physical analyses. Thus, a co-moving observer 0 provides a baseline for measuring the true physical characteristics of a system, unaffected by the observer's movement, a co-moving observer is measuring 'das Ding an sich', the entity as it is, "... das, was der Erscheinung der Materie, als Ding an sich selbst, zum Grunde liegt ..." (see Kant, 1790, p. 428). Kant's assertion that the 'thing-in-itself' (Ding an sich) cannot be known ("... wie Dinge an sich selbst ... seyn mögen, ist gänzlich außer unsrer Erkenntnißsphäre" (see Kant, 1790, p. 235)) is a central theme in his work 'Critique of Pure Reason' (Critik der reinen Vernunft). Specifically, Kant argues that human perception and understanding are limited to phenomena or things as they appear to us ("Erscheinungen sind keine Dinge an sich selbst" (see Kant, 1790, p. 206)) and cannot grasp noumena (things as they are in themselves).

Example A wave travelling at the speed of light which is measured by another wave travelling at the same speed of light but with a different wavelength, the primary consequences could include Doppler shifts in frequency and wavelength, potential interference patterns, and the intrinsic relationship between frequency, wavelength, and the speed of light. The relative velocity between both is 0.

Relativistic observer R

An observer R is an observer who is either at rest ($v = 0$) relative to a specific inertial frame of reference or who is moving at constant velocity v relative to a specific inertial frame of reference. In the context of special relativity, an observer R would account for time dilation, length contraction, and other relativistic phenomena due to their relative velocity v . This observer can be either in a state of rest with respect to an inertial frame of reference or travelling at constant velocity relative to such an inertial frame of reference.

Newton's law of gravitation

Isaac Newton first formulated his version of the law of universal gravitation in his book *Philosophiæ Naturalis Principia Mathematica* (often referred to simply as the *Principia*), which was published in 1687. The law of universal gravitation can be found in *Liber primus* (pp. 26-235), Proposition 75 (pp. 197-198), and explicitly in *Liber tertius* (pp. 401-510), Proposition 7, Theorem 7 (pp. 411-412). The algebraic form of Newton's law of gravitation, which is familiar today, states in its classical form that the gravitational force $\mathbf{F}_R$ between two point masses m_{R1} and m_{R2} is given by:

$$F_R = G_R \times \left(\frac{m_{1R} \times m_{2R}}{d_R^2} \right) \quad (3)$$

where:

- G_R is the gravitational constant from the point of view the relativistic observer,
- m_{1R} is the mass 1 from the point of view of a relativistic observer,
- m_{2R} is the mass 2 from the point of view of a relativistic observer,
- d_R is the distance between the two masses.

2.2. Differential geometry

2.3. Tensor Algebra

Geometry can be traced back to the first trials of systematic logical thinking of humans. Still, the nature of the relation between the definitions, axioms, theorems, and proofs in a system of geometry and objective reality has to be considered in detail. Tensors are one mathematical approach to geometry. The tensor (see also [Voigt, 1898](#), p. 20) calculus has been developed in some greater detail by Ricci-Curbastro (see [Ricci-Curbastro and Levi-Civita, 1900](#)) and his student Levi-Civita on the basis of earlier work of authors like Riemann, Christoffel, Bianchi and others. Especially, Einstein's general theory of relativity is expressed by the mathematical technology of tensors.

2.3.1. Tensor addition

Definition 2.1 (Tensor addition).

The sum of two second rank co-variant tensors has the properties of associativity and commutativity and is defined as

$$\begin{aligned} C_{\mu\nu} &\equiv A_{\mu\nu} + B_{\mu\nu} \\ &\equiv B_{\mu\nu} + A_{\mu\nu} \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

The sum of two second rank contra-variant tensors has the properties of associativity and commutativity and is defined as

$$\begin{aligned} C^{\mu\nu} &\equiv A^{\mu\nu} + B^{\mu\nu} \\ &\equiv B^{\mu\nu} + A^{\mu\nu} \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

The sum of two second rank mixed tensors has the properties of associativity and commutativity and is defined as

$$\begin{aligned} C_{\mu}{}^{\nu} &\equiv A_{\mu}{}^{\nu} + B_{\mu}{}^{\nu} \\ &\equiv B_{\mu}{}^{\nu} + A_{\mu}{}^{\nu} \end{aligned} \quad (6)$$

2.3.2. Anti tensor I

Definition 2.2 (Anti tensor I).

Let $a_{\mu\nu}$ denote a co-variant (lower index) second-rank tensor. Let $b_{\mu\nu}$, $c_{\mu\nu}$ et cetera denote other co-variant second-rank tensors. Let $E_{\mu\nu}$ denote the sum of these co-variant second-rank tensors. Let the relationship $a_{\mu\nu} + b_{\mu\nu} + c_{\mu\nu} + \dots \equiv E_{\mu\nu}$ be given. A co-variant second-rank anti tensor (see also [Barukčić, 2020](#)) of a tensor $a_{\mu\nu}$ denoted in general as $\underline{a}_{\mu\nu}$ is defined

$$\begin{aligned} \underline{a}_{\mu\nu} &\equiv E_{\mu\nu} - a_{\mu\nu} \\ &\equiv b_{\mu\nu} + c_{\mu\nu} + \dots \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

2.3.3. Anti tensor II

Definition 2.3 (Anti tensor II).

Let $a^{\mu\nu}$ denote a contra-variant (upper index) second-rank tensor. Let $b^{\mu\nu}$, $c^{\mu\nu}$ et cetera denote other contra-variant (upper index) second-rank tensors. Let $E^{\mu\nu}$ denote the sum of these contra-variant (upper index) second-rank tensors. Let the relationship $a^{\mu\nu} + b^{\mu\nu} + c^{\mu\nu} + \dots \equiv E^{\mu\nu}$ be given. A co-variant second-rank anti tensor of a tensor $a^{\mu\nu}$ denoted in general as $\underline{a}^{\mu\nu}$ is defined

$$\begin{aligned}\underline{a}^{\mu\nu} &\equiv E^{\mu\nu} - a^{\mu\nu} \\ &\equiv b^{\mu\nu} + c^{\mu\nu} + \dots\end{aligned}\quad (8)$$

2.3.4. Anti tensor III

Definition 2.4 (Anti tensor III).

Let a_{μ}^{ν} denote a mixed second-rank tensor. Let b_{μ}^{ν} , c_{μ}^{ν} et cetera denote other mixed second-rank tensors. Let E_{μ}^{ν} denote the sum of these mixed second-rank tensors. Let the relationship $a_{\mu}^{\nu} + b_{\mu}^{\nu} + c_{\mu}^{\nu} + \dots \equiv E_{\mu}^{\nu}$ be given. A mixed second-rank anti tensor of a tensor a_{μ}^{ν} denoted in general as $\underline{a}_{\mu}^{\nu}$ is defined

$$\begin{aligned}\underline{a}_{\mu}^{\nu} &\equiv E_{\mu}^{\nu} - a_{\mu}^{\nu} \\ &\equiv b_{\mu}^{\nu} + c_{\mu}^{\nu} + \dots\end{aligned}\quad (9)$$

2.3.5. Tensor subtraction

Definition 2.5 (Tensor subtraction).

The subtraction of two second rank co-variant tensors is defined as

$$C_{\mu\nu} \equiv A_{\mu\nu} - B_{\mu\nu} \quad (10)$$

The subtraction of two second rank contra-variant tensors is defined as

$$C^{\mu\nu} \equiv A^{\mu\nu} - B^{\mu\nu} \quad (11)$$

The subtraction of two second rank mixed tensors is defined as

$$C_{\mu}^{\nu} \equiv A_{\mu}^{\nu} - B_{\mu}^{\nu} \quad (12)$$

2.3.6. Symmetric and anti symmetric tensors

Definition 2.6 (Symmetric and anti symmetric tensors).

Symmetric tensors of rank 2 may represent many physical properties objective reality. A co-variant second-rank tensor $a_{\mu\nu}$ is symmetric if

$$a_{\mu\nu} \equiv a_{\nu\mu} \quad (13)$$

However, there are circumstances, where a tensor is anti-symmetric. A co-variant second-rank tensor $a_{\mu\nu}$ is anti-symmetric if

$$a_{\mu\nu} \equiv -a_{\nu\mu} \quad (14)$$

Thus far, there are circumstances were an anti-tensor is identical with an anti-symmetrical tensor.

$$a_{\mu\nu} \equiv E_{\mu\nu} - b_{\mu\nu} + \dots \equiv E_{\mu\nu} - \underline{a}_{\mu\nu} \equiv -a_{\nu\mu} \quad (15)$$

Under conditions where $E_{\mu\nu} = 0$, an anti-tensor is identical with an anti-symmetrical tensor or it is

$$-\underline{a}_{\mu\nu} \equiv -a_{\nu\mu} \quad (16)$$

However, an anti-tensor is not identical with an anti-symmetrical tensor as such.

Definition 2.7 (Multiplication of tensors). *Let g_{kl} or $g_{\mu\nu}$ denote a 2-index metric tensors. Let $g_{kl\mu\nu}$ denote a 4-index metric tensors. Let $g_{kl\mu\nu\dots}$ denote a n-th index metric tensor. The n-index metric tensor $g_{kl\mu\nu\dots}$ itself is a covariant symmetric tensor and equally an example of a tensor field. If we pause for a moment today and rely on Einstein's "Die Grundlage der allgemeinen Relativitätstheorie" (see [Einstein, 1916](#), p. 784), it is*

$$g_{kl\mu\nu} \equiv g_{kl}g_{\mu\nu} \quad (17)$$

and in the case of n-th rank order

$$g_{kl\mu\nu\dots} \equiv g_{kl}g_{\mu\nu\dots} \quad (18)$$

The mixed and contra-variant cases are similar. Riemann defined the distance between two neighbouring points more or less by a quadratic differential form. The geometry based on the positive definite Riemannian metric tensor is called the Riemannian geometry. However, tensor calculus as a generalization of classical linear algebra should assure that formulae are invariant under coordinate transformations and that the same are independent of any kind of the rank order of the metric tensor chosen. Albert Einstein (see [Einstein, 1916](#)) presented some rules of tensor algebra in his important publication issued in the year 1916.

$$T_{a\ b\ c} \equiv A_{a\ b}B_c \quad (19)$$

(see [Einstein, 1916](#), p. 784)

Furthermore, it is

$$T^{abcd} \equiv A^a B^b C^c D^d \quad (20)$$

(see Einstein, 1916, p. 784)

and equally

$$T^{\quad ab}_{\quad cd} \equiv A^a B^b C_c D_d \quad (21)$$

(see Einstein, 1916, p. 784)

A covariant tensor of the second rank type is defined as

$$T_{cd} \equiv A_c B_d \quad (22)$$

(see Einstein, 1916, p. 782)

The mathematics of tensors is particularly useful for Einstein's general theory of relativity. In a D -dimensional space a tensor of rank n has D^n components. A contravariant tensor of the second rank type is defined as

$$T^{cd} \equiv A^c B^d \quad (23)$$

(see Einstein, 1916, p. 782)

A mixed tensor of the second rank type is defined by Einstein as follows.

$$T^{\quad c \quad d}_{\quad} \equiv A_c B^d \quad (24)$$

(see Einstein, 1916, p. 783)

A scalar F , or a tensor of zero rank, is given by the relationship

$$F \equiv F^{\quad b}_{\quad b} \equiv F^{\quad a \quad b}_{\quad a \quad b} \equiv F_{ab} F^{ab} \quad (25)$$

(see Einstein, 1916, p. 785)

This relationship (see equation 25, p. 15) is of importance for the fundamental invariants of the electromagnetic field too. The covariant and contravariant products of two rank 2 tensors give the same value and result in a scalar. In general, scalar products are operations on two tensors of the same rank that yield a scalar.

2.3.7. The metric tensor $g_{\mu\nu}$ and the inverse metric tensor $g^{\mu\nu}$

General relativity is a theory of the geometrical properties of space-time, while the metric tensor $g_{\mu\nu}$ itself is of fundamental importance for general relativity. The metric tensor $g_{\mu\nu}$ is something like the generalization of the Pythagorean theorem. Thus far, it does not appear to be necessary to restrict the validity of the Pythagorean theorem only to certain situations. The question is justified why the Riemannian geometry should be oppressed by the quadratic restriction. In this context, **Finsler geometry**, named after Paul Finsler (1894 - 1970) who studied it in his doctoral thesis (see [Finsler, 1918](#)) in 1918, appears to be a kind of metric generalization of Riemannian geometry without the quadratic restriction and justifies the attempt to systematize and to extend the possibilities of general relativity.

Definition 2.8 (Kronecker delta).

The Kronecker delta (see [Zehfuss, 1858](#)) is a so called invariant tensor and has been invented by Leopold Kronecker (1823-1891) in 1868 (see [Kronecker, 1868](#)). Meanwhile, Kronecker delta appears in many areas of physics, mathematics, and engineering and is defined as

$$g_{\mu\rho} \times g^{\nu\rho} \equiv g_{\mu}^{\nu} \equiv \delta_{\mu}^{\nu} \quad (26)$$

Technically, the Kronecker delta itself is a mixed second-rank tensor.

Definition 2.9 (The metric tensor $g_{\mu\nu}$ and the inverse metric tensor $g^{\mu\nu}$).

The distance between any two points in a given space can be described geometrically by a generalized Pythagorean theorem, the metric tensor $g_{\mu\nu}$. Sharing Einstein's point of view, it is in general

$$g_{\mu\nu} \times g^{\mu\nu} \equiv \delta_{\nu}^{\nu} \equiv D \quad (27)$$

where D might denote the number of space-time dimensions. The quantity

$$\delta_i^i \equiv \delta_1^1 + \delta_2^2 + \dots + \delta_D^D \equiv D \quad (28)$$

is an invariant. In other words, an index which is repeated inside an expression means summation over the repeated index (Einstein summation convention). Vectors and scalars are invariant under coordinate transformations. In point of fact, Einstein field equations ([Einstein, 1915, 1916, 1917, 1935](#); [Einstein and Sitter, 1932](#)) were initially formulated by Einstein himself in the context of a four-dimensional theory even though Einstein field equations need not to break down under conditions of D space-time dimensions (see [Stephani, 2003](#)). Nonetheless, based on Einstein's statement ([Einstein, 1916, p. 796](#)), one gets (see also [Einstein, 1923b, p. 91](#))

$$g_{\mu\nu} \times g^{\mu\nu} \equiv \delta_{\nu}^{\nu} \equiv D \equiv +4 \quad (29)$$

or

$$\frac{1}{g_{\mu\nu} \times g^{\mu\nu}} \equiv \frac{1}{4} \quad (30)$$

where $g^{\mu\nu}$ is the matrix inverse of the metric tensor $g_{\mu\nu}$. The inverse metric tensor or the metric tensor, which is always symmetric, allow tensors to be transformed into each other and are used to lower and raise indices. Einstein's pointed out that

“... the tensor $g_{\mu\nu}$ of the gravitational potential”
(Einstein, 1923b, p. 88)

The metric tensor $g_{\mu\nu}$, a very important concept in differential geometry and general relativity, provides among other a way to describe the geometric and causal structure of various manifolds, including spacetime itself.

Definition

The metric tensor $g_{\mu\nu}$ is a mathematical object which defines the distance between two points in a given space or spacetime represented by a symmetric, non-degenerate, rank-2 tensor field. In n -dimensional space, the metric tensor is an $n \times n$ matrix at each point in the space.

Mathematical Representation

In a coordinate system x^μ , the metric tensor is typically denoted by $g_{\mu\nu}$ and offers possibilities to compute lengths and angles in the space. The line element ds^2 , which represents the squared infinitesimal distance between two points, is given by:

$$ds^2 = g_{\mu\nu} dx^\mu dx^\nu \quad (31)$$

where:

- $g_{\mu\nu}$ are the components of the metric tensor.
- dx^μ and dx^ν are differential displacements in the coordinates.

Metric tensor: Some properties

1. **Symmetry:** The metric tensor is symmetric, meaning $g_{\mu\nu} = g_{\nu\mu}$.
2. **Non-Degeneracy:** The determinant of the metric tensor $\det(g_{\mu\nu}) \neq 0$.

-
3. **Signature:** In general relativity, the metric tensor of spacetime typically has a Lorentzian signature, often $(- + ++)$ or $(+ - --)$, distinguishing time from spatial dimensions.

Functions

1. **Distance and Angles:** The metric tensor is used to compute the length of curves, areas, volumes, and angles between vectors.
2. **Raising and Lowering Indices:** The metric tensor can raise and lower indices of tensors. For a vector v^μ , the lower index is obtained by $v_\nu = g_{\mu\nu}v^\mu$.
3. **Curvature:** The metric tensor is used to calculate the curvature of the space or spacetime via the Riemann curvature tensor, Ricci curvature tensor, and scalar curvature.
4. **Geodesics:** It determines the paths of free-falling particles in spacetime, which are geodesics (paths of shortest distance or extremal aging).

Metric tensor: General Relativity

In the context of general relativity, the metric tensor describes the gravitational field. Einstein's field equations relate the metric tensor to the energy-momentum tensor, providing a description of how matter and energy influence the curvature of spacetime:

$$G_{\mu\nu} + \Lambda g_{\mu\nu} = \kappa T_{\mu\nu} \quad (32)$$

where $G_{\mu\nu}$ is the Einstein tensor derived from the metric tensor, $T_{\mu\nu}$ is the energy-momentum tensor, and κ is a constant.

Metric tensor: special cases

1. **Flat Space (Euclidean Metric):** In three-dimensional Euclidean space, the metric tensor can be represented as a simple identity matrix:

$$g_{\mu\nu} = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix} \quad (33)$$

2. **Minkowski Metric:** For flat spacetime in special relativity:

$$\eta_{\mu\nu} = \begin{bmatrix} -1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix} \quad (34)$$

3. Schwarzschild Metric:

The Schwarzschild metric (see [Schwarzschild, 1916](#), pp. 189-196) is a solution to Einstein's field equations in General Relativity that describes the gravitational field outside a spherical, non-rotating mass such as a planet or black hole. It represents the spacetime geometry around such a mass, providing a way to calculate the effects of gravity in a spherically symmetric system. The Schwarzschild metric is fundamental in understanding phenomena like black holes and planetary orbits in strong gravitational fields. The Schwarzschild metric ${}_{\text{Sch}}g_{\mu\nu}$ which reveals how spacetime is curved by mass is given as:

$$ds^2 = -\left(1 - \frac{2GM}{c^2 r}\right) c^2 dt^2 + \left(1 - \frac{2GM}{c^2 r}\right)^{-1} dr^2 + r^2 d\theta^2 + r^2 \sin^2 \theta d\phi^2 \quad (35)$$

Here, G is the gravitational constant, M is the mass of the central object, r is the radial coordinate, θ is the polar angle, and ϕ is the azimuthal angle. In matrix form, the Schwarzschild metric can be written as:

$${}_{\text{Sch}}g_{\mu\nu} = \begin{bmatrix} -\left(1 - \frac{2GM}{r}\right) & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \left(1 - \frac{2GM}{r}\right)^{-1} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & r^2 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & r^2 \sin^2 \theta \end{bmatrix} \quad (36)$$

The inverse Schwarzschild metric tensor $g^{\mu\nu}$ is given as:

$${}_{\text{Sch}}g^{\mu\nu} = \begin{bmatrix} -\frac{1}{1 - \frac{2GM}{r}} & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 - \frac{2GM}{r} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & \frac{1}{r^2} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & \frac{1}{r^2 \sin^2 \theta} \end{bmatrix} \quad (37)$$

The Schwarzschild metric describes the spacetime geometry around a spherically symmetric, non-rotating mass in General Relativity, but it does not directly incorporate electromagnetic effects. The Schwarzschild metric specifically describes the spacetime geometry of a non-rotating, uncharged black hole (see [Michell, 1784](#)). It provides insights into the structure of the event horizon, singularity, and the surrounding spacetime curvature. The metric reveals that the spacetime curvature becomes infinitely large at the singularity, located at the center of the black hole, and that the event horizon acts as a boundary beyond which nothing can escape. It also describes how objects move and time behaves in the vicinity of a black hole. The Schwarzschild solution is crucial for understanding black holes in the context of General Relativity, forming the basis for more complex models involving rotating or charged black holes.

Identity and Difference Between the Schwarzschild Metric Tensor and the Metric Tensor of General Relativity

In general, the **Metric Tensor of General Relativity** represents the most general form of spacetime geometry, encoding the curvature due to mass-energy distributions and varying across different spacetimes. In contrast to this, the **Schwarzschild Metric Tensor** is a specific instance of the metric tensor for a static, non-rotating mass in a vacuum, assuming spherical symmetry. The **Metric Tensor of General Relativity** is applicable to any gravitational system described by General Relativity, including complex and dynamic systems while the **Schwarzschild Metric Tensor** is applicable specifically to the case of a spherically symmetric mass in a vacuum. In other words, the Schwarzschild metric tensor is a specific solution to the Einstein field equations in General Relativity which captures the curvature of spacetime due to a central mass and is a particular example of the more general metric tensor in General Relativity. The anti tensor $\underline{\text{Sch}}g_{\mu\nu}$ represents the difference between a metric tensor $g_{\mu\nu}$ of general relativity and the Schwarzschild metric tensor $\text{Sch}g_{\mu\nu}$. This anti-tensor encapsulates the other tensor of the Schwarzschild metric tensor, the complementary metric, the opposite metric of the Schwarzschild metric and is defined as:

$$\underline{\text{Sch}}g_{\mu\nu} = g_{\mu\nu} - \text{Sch}g_{\mu\nu} \quad (38)$$

The resulting anti tensor $\underline{\text{Sch}}g_{\mu\nu}$ captures deviations from the Schwarzschild solution due to additional mass and energy or curvature. In general, the metric tensor $g_{\mu\nu}$ of general relativity can be decomposed as:

$$g_{\mu\nu} = \text{OM}g_{\mu\nu} + \text{EM}g_{\mu\nu} \quad (39)$$

where

1. $g_{\mu\nu}$ is the metric tensor of general relativity.
2. $\text{OM}g_{\mu\nu}$ is the metric tensor of ordinary matter
3. $\text{EM}g_{\mu\nu}$ is the metric tensor of the electromagnetic field.

We define $\text{EM}g_{\mu\nu} = g_{\mu\nu} - \text{OM}g_{\mu\nu}$. In general, it is

$$g_{\mu\nu} = g_{\mu\nu} - \text{OM}g_{\mu\nu} + \text{OM}g_{\mu\nu} = \text{OM}g_{\mu\nu} + \text{EM}g_{\mu\nu} = \underline{\text{Sch}}g_{\mu\nu} + \text{Sch}g_{\mu\nu} \quad (40)$$

and

$$\text{EM}g_{\mu\nu} = \underline{\text{Sch}}g_{\mu\nu} + \text{Sch}g_{\mu\nu} - \text{OM}g_{\mu\nu} \quad (41)$$

Under conditions where $\text{Sch}g_{\mu\nu} - \text{OM}g_{\mu\nu} = 0$, it is

$$\text{EM}g_{\mu\nu} = \underline{\text{Sch}}g_{\mu\nu} \quad (42)$$

but not in general.

Metric Tensor and the Pythagorean Theorem

The metric tensor is more or less a generalization of the Pythagorean theorem to spaces that may be curved or have more than three dimensions.

Theorem

The Einstein metric tensor can be derived from the Pythagorean theorem.

Proof

1. Let's start with the identity $1 = 1$:

$$1 = 1$$

2. Multiply both sides by c^2 :

$$c^2 = c^2$$

3. Substitute c with the length of the hypotenuse of a right-angled triangle, according to the Pythagorean theorem:

$$c^2 = a^2 + b^2$$

4. This can be generalized to describe the distance in a Euclidean space with Cartesian coordinates. For an infinitesimal line element ds in two-dimensional space:

$$ds^2 = dx^2 + dy^2$$

5. This can be further generalized to n -dimensional space:

$$ds^2 = \sum_{i=1}^n (dx^i)^2$$

6. The expression $ds^2 = g_{ij}dx^i dx^j$ is the general form of a line element, where g_{ij} is the metric tensor and dx^i are the differential coordinates. In Euclidean space, the metric tensor is simply the identity matrix $g_{ij} = \delta_{ij}$, where δ_{ij} is the Kronecker delta:

$$g_{ij} = \delta_{ij} = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } i = j \\ 0 & \text{if } i \neq j \end{cases}$$

7. In a curved space, as described in general relativity, the metric tensor g_{ij} is generally not the identity matrix but a function of the spacetime coordinates. The distance between two points in this space is given by:

$$ds^2 = g_{ij}dx^i dx^j$$

8. This shows that the metric tensor g_{ij} is a generalization of the Pythagorean theorem that allows distances to be calculated in curved spaces.

9. To transition from the general form of the line element to the specific form used in general relativity, we note that in four-dimensional spacetime, the metric tensor is denoted as $g_{\mu\nu}$ and the coordinates are typically $x^\mu = (t, x, y, z)$. Therefore, the line element in four-dimensional spacetime is:

$$ds^2 = g_{\mu\nu}dx^\mu dx^\nu$$

Quod errat demonstrandum.

Thus, we have proven that the Einstein metric tensor can be derived from the Pythagorean theorem by generalizing the concept of distance to curved space.

Definition 2.10 (The metric tensor $g_{\mu\nu}$ decomposed). *The fundamental difference between the metric tensors of the four basic fields of nature, denoted as $a_{\mu\nu}$, $b_{\mu\nu}$, $c_{\mu\nu}$ and $d_{\mu\nu}$, finds its complete expression in equation 43 as*

$${}_a g_{\mu\nu} + {}_b g_{\mu\nu} + {}_c g_{\mu\nu} + {}_d g_{\mu\nu} \equiv g_{\mu\nu} \quad (43)$$

where ${}_a g_{\mu\nu}$ is the metric tensor of the ordinary matter, ${}_b g_{\mu\nu}$ is the metric tensor of electromagnetism, ${}_c g_{\mu\nu}$ is the metric tensor of the field $c_{\mu\nu}$, ${}_d g_{\mu\nu}$ is the metric tensor of the field $d_{\mu\nu}$ and $g_{\mu\nu}$ is the metric tensor of Einstein's general theory of relativity. We distinguish here between the four basic field of nature, as follows. Details are illustrated by table 1.

Table 1. The metric field decomposed

		Curvature		
		YES	NO	
Momentum	YES	(${}_a g_{\mu\nu}$)	(${}_b g_{\mu\nu}$)	(${}_E g_{\mu\nu}$)
	NO	(${}_d g_{\mu\nu}$)	(${}_d g_{\mu\nu}$)	(${}_E g_{\mu\nu}$)
		(${}_G g_{\mu\nu}$)	(${}_G g_{\mu\nu}$)	($g_{\mu\nu}$)

As an example, it is

$$\frac{R}{D} \times {}_a g_{\mu\nu} = a \times g_{\mu\nu} \quad (44)$$

and

$${}_a g_{\mu\nu} = \frac{a \times D}{R} \times g_{\mu\nu} \quad (45)$$

We obtain

$$\underbrace{\left(\frac{R}{D} \times a g_{\mu\nu}\right)}_{a_{\mu\nu}} + \underbrace{\left(\frac{R}{D} \times b g_{\mu\nu}\right)}_{b_{\mu\nu}} + \underbrace{\left(\frac{R}{D} \times c g_{\mu\nu}\right)}_{c_{\mu\nu}} + \underbrace{\left(\frac{R}{D} \times d g_{\mu\nu}\right)}_{d_{\mu\nu}} = \frac{R}{D} \times g_{\mu\nu} = R_{\mu\nu} \quad (46)$$

In this publication, let $a_{\mu\nu}$, $b_{\mu\nu}$, $c_{\mu\nu}$ and $d_{\mu\nu}$ denote the covariant second rank tensors of the four basic fields of nature were $a_{\mu\nu} \equiv a \times g_{\mu\nu}$ is the stress-energy tensor of ordinary matter, $b_{\mu\nu} \equiv b \times g_{\mu\nu}$, $c_{\mu\nu} \equiv c \times g_{\mu\nu}$ and $d_{\mu\nu} \equiv d \times g_{\mu\nu}$ et cetera.

Definition 2.11 (The metric tensor $g_{\mu\nu}$ of gravitational waves). Let $g_{\mu\nu}$ denote the metric tensor of Einstein's general theory of relativity. Let $g_w g_{\mu\nu}$ denote the metric tensor of **gravitational waves** of Einstein's general theory of relativity. Let $\underline{g_w} g_{\mu\nu}$ denote the metric tensor of **anti-gravitational waves** of Einstein's general theory of relativity. In general, there are circumstances where

$${}_E g_{\mu\nu} \equiv g_w g_{\mu\nu} + \underline{g_w} g_{\mu\nu} \quad (47)$$

Definition 2.12 (The metric tensor $\eta_{\mu\nu}$ of special relativity). There is a fundamental difference between Einstein's special theory of relativity and Einstein's general theory of relativity regarding the metric tensor. Let $\eta_{\mu\nu}$ denote the metric tensor of Einstein's special theory of relativity. In general,

depending upon circumstances, it is $\eta_{\mu\nu} = \begin{Bmatrix} -1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & -1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & -1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & +1 \end{Bmatrix}$ (see [Einstein, 1916](#), p. 778). Let $\underline{\eta}_{\mu\nu}$

denote **the anti-metric tensor of Einstein's special theory of relativity**. Let $g_{\mu\nu}$ denote the metric tensor of Einstein's general theory of relativity. In general, it is (see equation 7)

$$g_{\mu\nu} \equiv \eta_{\mu\nu} + \underline{\eta}_{\mu\nu} \quad (48)$$

We can imagine that there may be circumstances where ${}_E g_{\mu\nu} \equiv g_w g_{\mu\nu} \equiv \underline{\eta}_{\mu\nu}$ applies. Whether this will be generally valid might be the subject of further investigation. The n -th index relationship follows (see equation 7) as

$$g_{kl\mu\nu\dots} \equiv \eta_{kl\mu\nu\dots} + \underline{\eta}_{kl\mu\nu\dots} \quad (49)$$

Einstein's field equations becomes

$$\underbrace{\left(\left(\frac{R}{D} - \frac{R}{2} + \Lambda\right) \times \eta_{\mu\nu}\right)}_{\text{special relativity metric}} + \underbrace{\left(\left(\frac{R}{D} - \frac{R}{2} + \Lambda\right) \times \underline{\eta}_{\mu\nu}\right)}_{\text{disturbances or ripples in the curvature of spacetime}} \equiv \underbrace{\left(\frac{4 \times 2 \times \pi \times \gamma \times T}{c^4 \times D}\right)}_{\text{stress energy-momentum tensor}} \times g_{\mu\nu} \quad (50)$$

Under conditions of $D=2$ space-time dimensions, the gravitational waves are related to Λ by the relationship

$$\Lambda \times \underline{\eta}_{\mu\nu} \quad (51)$$

Definition 2.13 (Index raising). According to Einstein (see also [Einstein, 1916](#), p. 790), it is

$$F_{\mu\nu} \equiv g_{\mu\alpha} g_{\nu\beta} F^{\alpha\beta} \quad (52)$$

and equally

$$F^{\mu\nu} \equiv g^{\mu\alpha} g^{\nu\beta} F_{\alpha\beta} \quad (53)$$

In other (Kay, 1988) words (see Einstein, 1916, p. 790), an order-2 tensor, twice multiplied by the contra-variant metric tensor and contracted (Einstein, 1916, p. 785) in different indices, raises each index. It is

$$F^{\begin{pmatrix} 1 & 3 \\ \mu & c \end{pmatrix}} \equiv g^{\begin{pmatrix} 1 & 2 \\ \mu & \nu \end{pmatrix}} \times g^{\begin{pmatrix} 3 & 4 \\ c & d \end{pmatrix}} \times F_{\begin{pmatrix} \nu & d \\ 2 & 4 \end{pmatrix}} \quad (54)$$

or more professionally

$$F^{\mu c} \equiv g^{\mu\nu} \times g^{cd} \times F_{\nu d} \quad (55)$$

Following Einstein, it is $g_{\mu\nu} \times g^{\mu\nu} \equiv \delta_{\mu}^{\mu}$ (Einstein, 1916, p. 796). Furthermore, in conjunction with another view of Einstein (see Einstein, 1916, p. 785), it is

$$F \equiv F_{\mu\nu}{}^{\mu\nu} \equiv F_{\mu\nu} \times F^{\mu\nu} \quad (56)$$

2.4. Einstein's general theory or relativity

Definition 2.14 (The Einstein field equations). The Einstein field equations (Einstein, 1915, 1916, 1917, 1935; Einstein and Sitter, 1932) describe the relationship between the presence of matter (represented by the stress-energy tensor $\left(\left(\frac{4 \times 2 \times \pi \times \gamma}{c^4}\right) \times T_{\mu\nu}\right)$) in a given region of space time and the curvature (represented by the Einstein tensor $G_{\mu\nu} = R_{\mu\nu} - \left(\left(\frac{R}{2}\right) \times g_{\mu\nu}\right)$) in that region of space time by the equation

$$R_{\mu\nu} - \left(\left(\frac{R}{2}\right) \times g_{\mu\nu}\right) + (\Lambda \times g_{\mu\nu}) \equiv \left(\frac{4 \times 2 \times \pi \times \gamma}{c^4}\right) \times T_{\mu\nu} \quad (57)$$

$$\equiv E_{\mu\nu}$$

where $R_{\mu\nu}$ is the Ricci tensor (Ricci-Curbastro and Levi-Civita, 1900) of 'Einstein's general theory of relativity' (Einstein, 1916), R is the Ricci scalar, the trace of the Ricci curvature tensor with respect to the metric and equally the simplest curvature invariant of a Riemannian manifold, Λ is the Einstein's cosmological (Barukčić, 2015a; Einstein, 1917) constant, $\underline{\Lambda}$ is the "anti cosmological constant" (Barukčić, 2015a), $g_{\mu\nu}$ is the metric tensor of Einstein's general theory of relativity, $G_{\mu\nu}$ is Einstein's curvature tensor, $\underline{G}_{\mu\nu}$ is the "anti tensor" (Barukčić, 2016c) of Einstein's curvature tensor, $E_{\mu\nu}$ is the stress-energy tensor of energy, $\underline{E}_{\mu\nu}$ is the tensor of non-energy, the anti-tensor of the stress-energy tensor of energy, $a_{\mu\nu}$, $b_{\mu\nu}$, $c_{\mu\nu}$ and $d_{\mu\nu}$ denote the four basic fields of nature were $a_{\mu\nu}$ is the stress-energy tensor of ordinary matter, $b_{\mu\nu}$ is the stress-energy tensor of the electromagnetic field, c is the speed of the light in vacuum, γ is Newton's gravitational "constant" (Barukčić, 2015a,b, 2016a,c), π is Archimedes constant pi.

Einstein's field equations are defined in space-time dimensions (see Málek, 2012, p. 31) other than 3+1 too. Table 2 may provide a more detailed and preliminary overview of the definitions (Barukčić, 2016b,c) before.

		Curvature		
		YES	NO	
Momentum	YES	$a_{\mu\nu}$	$b_{\mu\nu} \equiv (c_{\mu\nu} + \Lambda \times g_{\mu\nu})$	$\frac{8 \times \pi \times \gamma \times T}{c^4 \times D} \times g_{\mu\nu} \equiv \left(\frac{R}{D} - \frac{R}{2} + \Lambda\right) \times g_{\mu\nu}$
	NO	$c_{\mu\nu} \equiv (b_{\mu\nu} - \Lambda \times g_{\mu\nu})$	$d_{\mu\nu} \equiv \left(\frac{R}{2} \times g_{\mu\nu} - b_{\mu\nu}\right)$	$\left(\frac{R}{2} - \Lambda\right) \times g_{\mu\nu}$
		$G_{\mu\nu} \equiv \left(\frac{R}{D} - \frac{R}{2}\right) \times g_{\mu\nu}$	$\frac{R}{2} \times g_{\mu\nu}$	$R_{\mu\nu} \equiv \frac{R}{D} \times g_{\mu\nu}$

Table 2. Four basic fields of nature and the Einstein field equations.

From Einstein's specific point of view, two wings are necessary to get to the core of the relationship between matter and gravitational field, just as two wings are essential for a bird that conquers the air.

We are quite privileged to consider in detail that

$$\underbrace{\left(\frac{R}{D} \times g_{\mu\nu}\right) - \left(\left(\frac{R}{2}\right) \times g_{\mu\nu}\right) + (\Lambda \times g_{\mu\nu})}_{\text{the left-hand side}} \equiv \underbrace{\left(\frac{4 \times 2 \times \pi \times \gamma \times T}{c^4 \times D}\right) \times g_{\mu\nu}}_{\text{the right-hand side}} \quad (58)$$

while $R_{\mu\nu} \equiv a_{\mu\nu} + b_{\mu\nu} + c_{\mu\nu} + d_{\mu\nu}$ and the

“... one wing ... is made of fine marble (**left side of the equation**) ...

the other wing ... is built of low-grade wood (**right side of equation**).

The phenomenological representation of matter is, in fact, only a crude substitute for a representation which would do justice to all known properties of matter. ”

(Einstein, 1936, p. 370)

Taken together, the n^{th} index, D-dimensional Einstein’s gravitational field equations (Barukčić, 2020) follow as

$$\underbrace{\left(\frac{R}{D} \times g_{\mu\nu\rho\dots}\right) - \left(\left(\frac{R}{2}\right) \times g_{\mu\nu\rho\dots}\right) + (\Lambda \times g_{\mu\nu\rho\dots})}_{\text{(local) space-time curvature}} \equiv \underbrace{\left(\frac{4 \times 2 \times \pi \times \gamma \times T}{c^4 \times D}\right) \times g_{\mu\nu\rho\dots}}_{\text{(local) energy and momentum}} \quad (59)$$

Under conditions where

$$\frac{\left(\frac{R}{D} - \frac{R}{2} + \Lambda\right)}{\left(\frac{4 \times 2 \times \pi \times T}{c^4 \times D}\right)} \equiv \gamma \equiv \frac{F \times d^2}{m_1 \times m_1} \quad (60)$$

we would have to accept Newton’s law of gravitation given as

$$F = \frac{\left(\frac{R}{D} - \frac{R}{2} + \Lambda\right)}{\left(\frac{4 \times 2 \times \pi \times T}{c^4 \times D}\right)} \times \frac{m_1 \times m_1}{d^2} = D \times \frac{\hbar \times \left(\frac{R}{D} - \frac{R}{2} + \Lambda\right)}{h \times (4 \times T)} \times \frac{E_1 \times E_2}{d^2} \quad (61)$$

which is not without difficulties as such. Newton’s gravitational constant γ appears to us to be dependent at least on the number of space-time dimensions D as proposed by the following equation

$$\gamma = D \times \frac{\left(\frac{R}{D} - \frac{R}{2} + \Lambda\right)}{(4 \times 2 \times \pi \times T)} \times c^4 \quad (62)$$

and may not be a constant. Equation 62 suggests an experimental possibility to determine the number of space-time dimensions D or of Λ et cetera experimentally. However and in general, the metric field

(responsible for gravitational-inertial properties of bodies) on the left-hand side of Einstein's field equations, is completely determined by a tensorial but non-geometrical phenomenological representation of matter on the right-hand side. Einstein himself had a very differentiated view of these two sides of his field equations. In point of fact, the left part of the Einstein field equations (the Einstein tensor) is taken by Einstein as fine marble because of its geometrical nature, whereas the right side of the equations is lacking similar geometric significance and was degraded by Einstein himself to low-grade wood, the need for geometrical unification follows at least from such an asymmetrical state of affairs. An incorporation of electromagnetism and of other fields into spacetime geometry is desirable. In point of fact, a striving toward unification and simplification of the premises and of Einstein's general theory of relativity as a whole is necessary.

“The mind striving after unification of the theory cannot be satisfied that two fields should exist which, by their nature, are quite independent. A mathematically **unified field theory** is sought in which **the gravitational field and the electromagnetic field are interpreted only as different components or manifestations of the same uniform field** ... The gravitational theory ... should be generalized so that it includes the laws of the electromagnetic field. ”

(Einstein, 1923a, p. 489)

Definition 2.15 (The stress-energy tensor of ordinary matter $a_{\mu\nu}$). *Howard Georgi and Sheldon Glashow (Georgi and Glashow, 1974) proposed in 1974 the first Grand Unified Theory (Buras et al., 1978). Grand Unified Theory (GUT) models predict the unification of the electromagnetic, the weak, and the strong forces into a single force. However, it appears to be more appropriate to unify the strong nuclear force and the weak nuclear force into an ordinary force. The matter as associated with an ordinary force can be calculated very precisely. Under conditions of Einstein's general (Einstein, 1915, 1916, 1917, 1935; Einstein and Sitter, 1932) theory of relativity, the stress-energy tensor of ordinary matter $a_{\mu\nu}$ which is expected to unify the strong nuclear force and the weak nuclear force into an ordinary force is defined / derived / determined as*

$$\begin{aligned}
 a_{\mu\nu} &\equiv \left(\left(\frac{4 \times 2 \times \pi \times \gamma}{c^4} \right) \times T_{\mu\nu} \right) - b_{\mu\nu} \\
 &\equiv G_{\mu\nu} + (\Lambda \times g_{\mu\nu}) - b_{\mu\nu} \\
 &\equiv R_{\mu\nu} - (R \times g_{\mu\nu}) + ((\Lambda \times g_{\mu\nu}) + d_{\mu\nu}) = 0 \\
 &\equiv \left(\left(\frac{R}{D} \right) \times g_{\mu\nu} \right) - (R \times g_{\mu\nu}) \\
 &\equiv (E - b) \times g_{\mu\nu} \\
 &\equiv (G - c) \times g_{\mu\nu} \\
 &\equiv a \times g_{\mu\nu}
 \end{aligned} \tag{63}$$

or

$$a_{\mu\nu} \equiv R_{\mu\nu} - \left(\left(\frac{R}{2} \right) \times g_{\mu\nu} \right) + (\Lambda \times g_{\mu\nu}) -$$

$$\left(\frac{1}{4 \times \pi} \times \left(F_{\mu c} \times F_{\nu d} \times g^{cd} \right) + \left(\frac{1}{4} \times g_{\mu\nu} \times F_{de} \times F^{de} \right) \right) \quad (64)$$

From our present point of view we can expect that there are conditions where

$$\begin{aligned} a_{\mu\nu} &\equiv \left(\left(\frac{4 \times 2 \times \pi \times \gamma}{c^4} \right) \times T_{\mu\nu} \right) - b_{\mu\nu} \\ &\equiv \left(\left(\frac{R}{D} - \frac{R}{2} + \Lambda \right) - \left(\frac{(4 + D) \times F_1}{4 \times \pi \times 4 \times D} \right) \right) \times g_{\mu\nu} \end{aligned} \quad (65)$$

where F_1 is Lorenz invariant.

Definition 2.16 (The 4-index D dimensional $a_{kl\mu\nu}$). The 4-index D dimensional $a_{kl\mu\nu}$ is defined as:

$$\begin{aligned} a_{kl\mu\nu} &\equiv (E - b) \times g_{kl\mu\nu} \\ &\equiv (G - c) \times g_{kl\mu\nu} \\ &\equiv a \times g_{kl\mu\nu} \end{aligned} \quad (66)$$

Definition 2.17 (The n-index D dimensional $a_{kl\mu\nu\dots}$). The n-index D dimensional $a_{kl\mu\nu\dots}$ is defined as:

$$\begin{aligned} a_{kl\mu\nu\dots} &\equiv (E - b) \times g_{kl\mu\nu\dots} \\ &\equiv (G - c) \times g_{kl\mu\nu\dots} \\ &\equiv a \times g_{kl\mu\nu\dots} \end{aligned} \quad (67)$$

Definition 2.18 (Ricci scalar R). Under conditions of Einstein's general (Einstein, 1915, 1916, 1917, 1935; Einstein and Sitter, 1932) theory of relativity, the Ricci scalar curvature R as the trace of the Ricci curvature tensor $R_{\mu\nu}$ with respect to the metric is a quantity which is determined at each point in space-time by lamda Λ and anti-lamda ($\underline{\Lambda}$) as

$$R \equiv g^{\mu\nu} \times R_{\mu\nu} \equiv (\Lambda) + (\underline{\Lambda}) \equiv D \times S \quad (68)$$

where D is proved as the number of space-time dimension and $S \equiv \left(\frac{R}{D} \right)$. A Ricci scalar curvature R which is positive at a certain point indicates that the volume of a small ball about the point has smaller volume than a ball of the same radius in Euclidean space. In other words, the density of space varies. In contrast to this, a Ricci scalar curvature R which is negative at a certain point indicates that the volume of a small ball is larger than it would be in Euclidean space. In general, it is (see Barukčić, 2015a)

$$R \times g_{\mu\nu} \equiv (\Lambda \times g_{\mu\nu}) + (\underline{\Lambda} \times g_{\mu\nu}) \quad (69)$$

or

$$R \equiv (\Lambda) + (\underline{\Lambda}) \quad (70)$$

The cosmological constant can also be written algebraically as part of the stress–energy tensor, a second order tensor as the source of gravity (energy density).

Under conditions where $R = 0$, it is

$$-(\Lambda) = +(\underline{\Lambda}) \quad (71)$$

Definition 2.19 (Ricci tensor $R_{\mu\nu}$). The Ricci tensor $R_{\mu\nu}$ is a geometric object which has been developed by Gregorio Ricci-Curbastro (1853 – 1925) (*Ricci-Curbastro and Levi-Civita, 1900*) and is able to measure of the degree to which a certain geometry of a given metric differs from that of ordinary Euclidean space. In this publication, let $a_{\mu\nu}$, $b_{\mu\nu}$, $c_{\mu\nu}$ and $d_{\mu\nu}$ denote the covariant second rank tensors of the four basic fields of nature were $a_{\mu\nu} \equiv \rho a^2 \times g_{\mu\nu}$ is the stress-energy tensor of ordinary matter, $b_{\mu\nu} \equiv \rho b^2 \times g_{\mu\nu}$ is the stress-energy tensor of the electromagnetic field, $c_{\mu\nu} \equiv c^2 \times g_{\mu\nu}$ is the tensor of the gravitational field and $d_{\mu\nu} \equiv \rho d^2 \times g_{\mu\nu}$ is the tensor of gravitational waves. The Ricci tensor $R_{\mu\nu}$ of ‘Einstein’s general theory of relativity’ (*Einstein, 1916*) is determined by the stress-energy tensor $\left(\left(\frac{4 \times 2 \times \pi \times \gamma}{c^4}\right) \times T_{\mu\nu}\right)$ and the anti stress-energy tensor $\left(\left(\left(\frac{R}{2}\right) \times g_{\mu\nu}\right) - (\Lambda \times g_{\mu\nu})\right)$ as

$$\begin{aligned} R_{\mu\nu} &\equiv \underbrace{\left(\left(\frac{4 \times 2 \times \pi \times \gamma}{c^4}\right) \times T_{\mu\nu}\right)}_{\text{stress-energy tensor}} + \underbrace{\left(\left(\left(\frac{R}{2}\right) \times g_{\mu\nu}\right) - (\Lambda \times g_{\mu\nu})\right)}_{\text{anti stress-energy tensor}} \\ &\equiv a_{\mu\nu} + b_{\mu\nu} + c_{\mu\nu} + d_{\mu\nu} \\ &\equiv (S) \times g_{\mu\nu} \\ &\equiv \left(\frac{R}{D}\right) \times g_{\mu\nu} \end{aligned} \quad (72)$$

while S might denote a scalar.

Definition 2.20 (Laue’s scalar T). Max von Laue (1879-1960) proposed the meanwhile so called Laue scalar (*Laue, 1911*) (criticised by Einstein (*Einstein and Grossmann, 1913; Norton, 1992*)) as the contraction of the the stress–energy momentum tensor $T_{\mu\nu}$ denoted as T and written without subscripts or arguments. Under conditions of Einstein’s general (*Einstein, 1915, 1916, 1917, 1935; Einstein and Sitter, 1932*) theory of relativity, it is

$$T \equiv g^{\mu\nu} \times T_{\mu\nu} \quad (73)$$

Taken Einstein seriously, $T_{\mu\nu}$ “denotes the co-variant energy tensor of matter” (see *Einstein, 1923b*, p. 88). In other words, “Considered phenomenologically, this energy tensor is composed of that of the electromagnetic field and of matter in the narrower sense.” (see *Einstein, 1923b*, p. 93)

Scalars are of use to describe circumstances of Einstein’s theory of general relativity. However, it is necessary to point out a crucial difference. The use of scalars should not be confused neither with Brans-Dicke (see *Brans and Dicke, 1961*) theory of gravitation (see *Norton, 1992*) nor with Nordström’s theory of gravitation (see *Nordström, 1913a,b*). The last has been found to be logically inconsistent.

Definition 2.21 (The scalar E). In general, we define the scalar E as

$$\begin{aligned}
 E &\equiv {}_d E_t^2 \equiv \left(\frac{8 \times \pi \times \gamma}{c^4 \times D} \right) \times T \\
 &\equiv \left(\frac{8 \times \pi \times \gamma \times T}{c^4 \times D} \right) \\
 &\equiv \left(\frac{2 \times \pi \times 4 \times \gamma \times T}{c^4 \times D} \right) \\
 &\equiv \left(\frac{h \times 4 \times \gamma \times T}{\hbar \times c^4 \times D} \right) \\
 &\equiv \left(\frac{R}{D} \right) - \left(\frac{R}{2} \right) + \Lambda
 \end{aligned} \tag{74}$$

where D is the space-time dimension, where c denote the speed of the light in vacuum, γ denote Newton's gravitational "constant" (Barukčić, 2015a,b, 2016a,c), π is the number pi and T denote Laue's scalar. The scalar E might correspond even to the total energy density squared of a (relativistic or quantum) system, and has the potential as such to bridge the gap between relativity theory and quantum mechanics under circumstances where the same is related or even identical with the Hamiltonian operator (squared).

Definition 2.22 (Stress-energy and momentum tensor $E_{\mu\nu}$). "Considered phenomenologically, this energy tensor is composed of that of the electromagnetic field and of matter in the narrower sense." (see also Einstein, 1923b, p. 93) The tensor of stress-energy-momentum denoted as $E_{\mu\nu}$ is determined in detail as follows.

$$\begin{aligned}
 E_{\mu\nu} &\equiv a_{\mu\nu} + b_{\mu\nu} \\
 &\equiv \left(\frac{4 \times 2 \times \pi \times \gamma}{c^4} \right) \times T_{\mu\nu} \\
 &\equiv \left(\frac{4 \times 2 \times \pi \times \gamma \times T}{c^4 \times D} \right) \times g_{\mu\nu} \\
 &\equiv R_{\mu\nu} - \left(\left(\frac{R}{2} \right) \times g_{\mu\nu} \right) + (\Lambda \times g_{\mu\nu}) \\
 &\equiv \left(S - \left(\frac{R}{2} \right) + \Lambda \right) \times g_{\mu\nu} \\
 &\equiv (G + \Lambda) \times g_{\mu\nu} \\
 &\equiv G_{\mu\nu} + (\Lambda \times g_{\mu\nu}) \\
 &\equiv R_{\mu\nu} - \underline{E}_{\mu\nu} \\
 &\equiv E \times g_{\mu\nu}
 \end{aligned} \tag{75}$$

while E might denote the scalar of, even something like 'energy density'. According to Einstein, it is necessary to consider that

“... a tensor, $T_{\mu\nu}$, of the second rank ... includes in itself the energy density of the electromagnetic field and of ponderable matter; we shall denote this in the following as the ‘energy tensor of matter’”

(Einstein, 1923b, pp. 87/88)

It is once again important to point out that all possible forms of energy and momentum are contained in the stress-energy tensor $T_{\mu\nu}$. This includes any matter present but if there is some electromagnetic radiation given then the same too must be included in $T_{\mu\nu}$. It goes without saying that in this case there is simply no energy or momentum left which could be assigned to the gravitational field. Therefore, assigning any kind of energy density to a gravitational field (see Einstein, 1918, pp. 156-159) could be difficult, both in principle and technically. The question inevitably arises why under the conditions of general relativity energy and momentum should be conserved at all?

Definition 2.23 (The scalar G). In general, we define the scalar G (Barukčić, 2020) as

$$\begin{aligned} G &\equiv {}_dG_t^2 \equiv \left(\left(\frac{R}{D} \right) - \frac{R}{2} \right) \\ &\equiv \left(E + {}_Rt_t - \frac{R}{2} \right) \\ &\equiv \left(E + \left(\frac{R}{2} - \Lambda \right) - \frac{R}{2} \right) \\ &\equiv E - \Lambda \end{aligned} \quad (76)$$

Definition 2.24 (Einstein’s curvature tensor $G_{\mu\nu}$). Under conditions of Einstein’s general (Einstein, 1915, 1916, 1917, 1935; Einstein and Sitter, 1932) theory of relativity, the tensor of curvature denoted by $G_{\mu\nu}$ is defined/derived/determined (see Barukčić, 2020) as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} G_{\mu\nu} &\equiv R_{\mu\nu} - \left(\left(\frac{R}{2} \right) \times g_{\mu\nu} \right) \\ &\equiv \left(\frac{R}{D} \right) \times g_{\mu\nu} - \left(\left(\frac{R}{2} \right) \times g_{\mu\nu} \right) \\ &\equiv \left(\left(\frac{R}{D} \right) - \frac{R}{2} \right) \times g_{\mu\nu} \\ &\equiv a_{\mu\nu} + c_{\mu\nu} \\ &\equiv G \times g_{\mu\nu} \\ &\equiv \left(\frac{R}{D} \right) \times {}_Gg_{\mu\nu} \end{aligned} \quad (77)$$

Definition 2.25 (The scalar $\underline{G}$). In general, we define the scalar $\underline{G}$ (see Barukčić, 2020) as

$$\begin{aligned} \underline{G} &\equiv {}_d\underline{G}_t^2 \equiv \left(\left(\frac{R}{D} \right) - G \right) \\ &\equiv \left(\frac{R}{2} \right) \end{aligned} \quad (78)$$

Definition 2.26 (The scalar $\underline{E}$). In general, we define the scalar $\underline{E}$ as (see Barukčić, 2020)

$$\begin{aligned}\underline{E} &\equiv {}_d\underline{E}^2 \equiv \left(\left(\frac{R}{D} \right) - E \right) \\ &\equiv \left(\frac{R}{2} - \Lambda \right)\end{aligned}\tag{79}$$

Remark 2.1. In the following of research, it is appropriate to prove the relationship between $(1/X)$ and the complex conjugate of the wave function Ψ^* or the identity $(1/X) \equiv \Psi^*$.

Definition 2.27 (The anti Einstein's curvature tensor or the tensor of non-curvature $\underline{G}_{\mu\nu}$). Under conditions of Einstein's general (Einstein, 1915, 1916, 1917, 1935; Einstein and Sitter, 1932) theory of relativity, the tensor of non-curvature is defined/derived/determined (Barukčić, 2020) as follows:

$$\begin{aligned}\underline{G}_{\mu\nu} &\equiv R_{\mu\nu} - G_{\mu\nu} \\ &\equiv R_{\mu\nu} - \left(R_{\mu\nu} - \left(\left(\frac{R}{2} \right) \times g_{\mu\nu} \right) \right) \\ &\equiv \left(\frac{R}{2} \right) \times g_{\mu\nu} \\ &\equiv b_{\mu\nu} + d_{\mu\nu} \\ &\equiv \underline{G} \times g_{\mu\nu}\end{aligned}\tag{80}$$

Definition 2.28 (The 4-index D dimensional stress-energy and momentum tensor $E_{kl\mu\nu}$). The 4-index D dimensional stress-energy-momentum tensor denoted as $E_{kl\mu\nu}$ is determined in detail as

$$\begin{aligned}E_{kl\mu\nu} &\equiv \left(\frac{8 \times \pi \times \gamma \times T}{c^4 \times D} \right) \times g_{kl\mu\nu} \\ &\equiv R_{kl\mu\nu} - \left(\left(\frac{R}{2} \right) \times g_{kl\mu\nu} \right) + \left(\Lambda \times g_{kl\mu\nu} \right) \\ &\equiv G_{kl\mu\nu} + \left(\Lambda \times g_{kl\mu\nu} \right) \\ &\equiv R_{kl\mu\nu} - \underline{E}_{kl\mu\nu} \\ &\equiv a_{kl\mu\nu} + b_{kl\mu\nu} \\ &\equiv H \times g_{kl\mu\nu} \equiv H_{kl\mu\nu} \\ &\equiv E \times g_{kl\mu\nu}\end{aligned}\tag{81}$$

Definition 2.29 (The n-index D dimensional stress-energy and momentum tensor $E_{kl\mu\nu\dots}$). The

n -index D dimensional stress-energy-momentum tensor denoted as $E_{kl\mu\nu\dots}$ is determined in detail as

$$\begin{aligned}
 E_{kl\mu\nu\dots} &\equiv \left(\frac{8 \times \pi \times \gamma \times T}{c^4 \times D} \right) \times g_{kl\mu\nu\dots} \\
 &\equiv R_{kl\mu\nu\dots} - \left(\left(\frac{R}{2} \right) \times g_{kl\mu\nu\dots} \right) + (\Lambda \times g_{kl\mu\nu\dots}) \\
 &\equiv G_{kl\mu\nu\dots} + (\Lambda \times g_{kl\mu\nu\dots}) \\
 &\equiv R_{kl\mu\nu\dots} - \underline{E}_{kl\mu\nu\dots} \\
 &\equiv a_{kl\mu\nu\dots} + b_{kl\mu\nu\dots} \\
 &\equiv H \times g_{kl\mu\nu\dots} \equiv H_{kl\mu\nu\dots} \\
 &\equiv E \times g_{kl\mu\nu\dots}
 \end{aligned} \tag{82}$$

Definition 2.30 (The tensor of non-energy $\underline{E}_{\mu\nu}$). Under conditions of Einstein's general (Einstein, 1915, 1916, 1917, 1935; Einstein and Sitter, 1932) theory of relativity, the tensor of non-energy or the anti tensor of the stress energy tensor is defined/derived/determined as follows:

$$\begin{aligned}
 \underline{E}_{\mu\nu} &\equiv R_{\mu\nu} - \left(\frac{4 \times 2 \times \pi \times \gamma}{c^4} \right) \times T_{\mu\nu} \\
 &\equiv \left(\left(\frac{R}{2} \right) \times g_{\mu\nu} \right) - (\Lambda \times g_{\mu\nu}) \\
 &\equiv \left(\left(\frac{R}{2} - \Lambda \right) \times g_{\mu\nu} \right) \\
 &\equiv c_{\mu\nu} + d_{\mu\nu} \\
 &\equiv \Psi \times g_{\mu\nu} \equiv \Psi_{\mu\nu} \\
 &\equiv \underline{E} \times g_{\mu\nu}
 \end{aligned} \tag{83}$$

Definition 2.31 (The 4-index D dimensional tensor of non-energy $\underline{E}_{kl\mu\nu}$). The 4-index D dimensional tensor (Einstein, 1915, 1916, 1917, 1935; Einstein and Sitter, 1932) of non-energy $\underline{E}_{kl\mu\nu}$ is defined as follows:

$$\begin{aligned}
 \underline{E}_{kl\mu\nu} &\equiv \left(\frac{R}{D} \times g_{kl\mu\nu} \right) - \left(\left(\frac{8 \times \pi \times \gamma \times T}{c^4 \times D} \right) \times g_{kl\mu\nu} \right) \\
 &\equiv \left(\left(\frac{R}{2} \right) \times g_{kl\mu\nu} \right) - (\Lambda \times g_{kl\mu\nu}) \\
 &\equiv \left(\left(\frac{R}{2} - \Lambda \right) \times g_{kl\mu\nu} \right) \\
 &\equiv c_{kl\mu\nu} + d_{kl\mu\nu} \\
 &\equiv \Psi \times g_{kl\mu\nu} \equiv \Psi_{kl\mu\nu} \\
 &\equiv \underline{E} \times g_{kl\mu\nu}
 \end{aligned} \tag{84}$$

Definition 2.32 (The n -th index D dimensional tensor of non-energy $\underline{E}_{kl\mu\nu\dots}$). The n -th index D dimensional tensor (Einstein, 1915, 1916, 1917, 1935; Einstein and Sitter, 1932) of non-energy $\underline{E}_{kl\mu\nu\dots}$

is defined as follows:

$$\begin{aligned}
 \underline{E}_{kl\mu\nu\dots} &\equiv \left(\frac{R}{D} \times g_{kl\mu\nu\dots} \right) - \left(\left(\frac{8 \times \pi \times \gamma \times T}{c^4 \times D} \right) \times g_{kl\mu\nu\dots} \right) \\
 &\equiv \left(\left(\frac{R}{2} \right) \times g_{kl\mu\nu\dots} \right) - \left(\Lambda \times g_{kl\mu\nu\dots} \right) \\
 &\equiv \left(\left(\frac{R}{2} - \Lambda \right) \times g_{kl\mu\nu\dots} \right) \\
 &\equiv c_{kl\mu\nu\dots} + d_{kl\mu\nu\dots} \\
 &\equiv \Psi \times g_{kl\mu\nu\dots} \equiv \Psi_{kl\mu\nu\dots} \\
 &\equiv \underline{E} \times g_{kl\mu\nu\dots}
 \end{aligned} \tag{85}$$

Definition 2.33 (The 4-index D dimensional Einstein's curvature tensor $G_{kl\mu\nu}$). The Riemann tensor $R_{kl\mu\nu}$ does not appear explicitly in Einstein's gravitational field equations. Therefore, the question is justified whether Einstein's equation of gravitation are really the most general equations. Frédéric Moulin proposed in the year 2017 a kind of a generalized 4-index gravitational field equation which contains the Riemann curvature tensor linearly (Moulin, 2017). Moulin himself ascribed an energy-momentum to the gravitational field itself (Moulin, 2017, p. 5/8) which is not without problems. Besides of all, it is known that the Riemann curvature tensor of general relativity $R_{kl\mu\nu}$ can be split into different ways, including the Weyl conformal tensor $C_{kl\mu\nu}$ and the anti-Weyl conformal tensor $\underline{C}_{kl\mu\nu}$ or in other words the parts which involve only the Ricci tensor $R_{\mu\nu}$ the curvature scalar R . Because of these properties ($R_{kl\mu\nu} \equiv C_{kl\mu\nu} + \underline{C}_{kl\mu\nu}$) it is possible to reformulate the famous Einstein equation. The 4-index D dimensional Einstein's curvature tensor (Einstein, 1915, 1916, 1917, 1935; Einstein and Sitter, 1932) denoted by $G_{kl\mu\nu}$ is defined (see Barukčić, 2020) as follows:

$$\begin{aligned}
 G_{kl\mu\nu} &\equiv R_{kl\mu\nu} - \left(\left(\frac{R}{2} \right) \times g_{kl\mu\nu} \right) \\
 &\equiv \left(\frac{R}{D} \right) \times g_{kl\mu\nu} - \left(\left(\frac{R}{2} \right) \times g_{kl\mu\nu} \right) \\
 &\equiv \left(\left(\frac{R}{D} - \frac{R}{2} \right) \times g_{kl\mu\nu} \right) \\
 &\equiv a_{kl\mu\nu} + c_{kl\mu\nu} \\
 &\equiv G \times g_{kl\mu\nu}
 \end{aligned} \tag{86}$$

Definition 2.34 (The n-index D dimensional Einstein's curvature tensor $G_{kl\mu\nu\dots}$). The n-index D dimensional Einstein's curvature tensor (Einstein, 1915, 1916, 1917, 1935; Einstein and Sitter, 1932) denoted by $G_{kl\mu\nu\dots}$ is defined (see Barukčić, 2020) as follows:

$$\begin{aligned}
G_{kl\mu\nu\dots} &\equiv R_{kl\mu\nu\dots} - \left(\left(\frac{R}{2} \right) \times g_{kl\mu\nu\dots} \right) \\
&\equiv \left(\frac{R}{D} \right) \times g_{kl\mu\nu\dots} - \left(\left(\frac{R}{2} \right) \times g_{kl\mu\nu\dots} \right) \\
&\equiv \left(\left(\frac{R}{D} \right) - \frac{R}{2} \right) \times g_{kl\mu\nu\dots} \\
&\equiv a_{kl\mu\nu\dots} + c_{kl\mu\nu\dots} \\
&\equiv G \times g_{kl\mu\nu\dots}
\end{aligned} \tag{87}$$

Definition 2.35 (The 4-index D dimensional anti Einstein's curvature tensor or the tensor or non-curvature $\underline{G}_{kl\mu\nu}$). The 4-index D dimensional anti Einstein's curvature tensor (Einstein, 1915, 1916, 1917, 1935; Einstein and Sitter, 1932) or the tensor of non-curvature denoted as $\underline{G}_{kl\mu\nu}$ is defined/derived/determined (Barukčić, 2020) as follows:

$$\begin{aligned}
\underline{G}_{kl\mu\nu} &\equiv R_{kl\mu\nu} - G_{kl\mu\nu} \\
&\equiv R_{kl\mu\nu} - \left(R_{kl\mu\nu} - \left(\left(\frac{R}{2} \right) \times g_{kl\mu\nu} \right) \right) \\
&\equiv \left(\frac{R}{2} \right) \times g_{kl\mu\nu} \\
&\equiv b_{kl\mu\nu} + d_{kl\mu\nu} \\
&\equiv \underline{G} \times g_{kl\mu\nu}
\end{aligned} \tag{88}$$

Definition 2.36 (The n-index D dimensional anti Einstein's curvature tensor or the tensor of non-curvature $\underline{G}_{kl\mu\nu\dots}$). The n-index D dimensional anti Einstein's curvature tensor or the tensor of non-curvature denoted as $\underline{G}_{kl\mu\nu\dots}$ is defined/derived/determined (Barukčić, 2020) as follows:

$$\begin{aligned}
\underline{G}_{kl\mu\nu\dots} &\equiv R_{kl\mu\nu\dots} - G_{kl\mu\nu\dots} \\
&\equiv R_{kl\mu\nu\dots} - \left(R_{kl\mu\nu\dots} - \left(\left(\frac{R}{2} \right) \times g_{kl\mu\nu\dots} \right) \right) \\
&\equiv \left(\frac{R}{2} \right) \times g_{kl\mu\nu\dots} \\
&\equiv b_{kl\mu\nu\dots} + d_{kl\mu\nu\dots} \\
&\equiv \underline{G} \times g_{kl\mu\nu\dots}
\end{aligned} \tag{89}$$

Definition 2.37 (The first quadratic Lorentz invariant F_1). The inner product of Faraday's electromagnetic field strength tensor yields a Lorentz invariant. The Lorentz invariant does not change from one frame of reference to another. The first quadratic Lorentz invariant, denoted as F_1 is determined as

$$F_1 \equiv F_{kl} \times F^{kl} \tag{90}$$

The electromagnetic field tensor F_{kl} has two Lorentz invariant quantities. One of the two fundamental Lorentz invariant quantities of the electromagnetic field (Escobar and Urrutia, 2014) is known be $F_{kl} \times F^{kl} = 2 \times (B^2 - E^2)$ where E denotes the electric E and B the magnetic field in the taken frame of reference.

Definition 2.38 (The second quadratic Lorentz invariant F_2). *The second quadratic Lorentz invariant, denoted as F_2 is determined as*

$$F_2 \equiv \epsilon^{klmn} \times F_{kl} \times F_{mn} \quad (91)$$

Definition 2.39 (The tensor $b_{\mu\nu}$). *The co-variant Minkowski's stress-energy tensor of the electromagnetic field, in this context denoted by $b_{\mu\nu}$, is of order two and its components can be displayed by a 4×4 matrix too. The trace of energy-momentum tensor of the electromagnetic field is known to be null. Under conditions of Einstein's general theory of relativity (Einstein, 1915, 1916, 1917, 1935; Einstein and Sitter, 1932), the tensor $b_{\mu\nu}$ denotes the trace-less, symmetric stress-energy tensor for source-free electromagnetic field is defined in cgs-Gaussian units (**depending upon metric signature**) as*

$$b_{\mu\nu} \equiv \left(\frac{1}{4 \times \pi} \times \left((F_{\mu c} \times F_{\nu}^c) + \left(\frac{1}{4} \times g_{\mu\nu} \times F_{de} \times F^{de} \right) \right) \right) \quad (92)$$

(see Lehmkuhl, 2011, p. 13) and equally as

$$b_{\mu\nu} \equiv \left(\frac{1}{4 \times \pi} \times \left((F_{\mu c} \times F_{\nu d} \times g^{cd}) - \left(\frac{1}{4} \times g_{\mu\nu} \times F_{de} \times F^{de} \right) \right) \right) \quad (93)$$

(see Hughston and Tod, 1990, p. 38)¹. The co-variant Minkowski's stress-energy tensor of the electromagnetic field is expressed under conditions of $D = 4$ space-time dimensions more compactly in a coordinate-independent (theorem 3.1, equation 80 Barukčić, 2020, p. 157) form as

$$\begin{aligned} b_{\mu\nu} &\equiv \left(\frac{1}{4 \times \pi} \times \left((F_{\mu c} \times F_{\nu d} \times g^{cd}) + \left(\frac{1}{4} \times g_{\mu\nu} \times F_{de} \times F^{de} \right) \right) \right) \\ &\equiv \left(\frac{1}{4 \times \pi} \times \left((F_{\mu c} \times F^{\mu c}) + \left(\frac{F_I}{4} \right) \right) \right) \times g_{\mu\nu} \\ &\equiv \left(\left(\frac{R}{D} \right) - a - c - d \right) \times g_{\mu\nu} \\ &\equiv (E - a) \times g_{\mu\nu} \\ &\equiv b \times g_{\mu\nu} \end{aligned} \quad (94)$$

where F_{de} is called the (traceless) Faraday/electromagnetic/field strength tensor.

Definition 2.40 (The 4-index D dimensional stress-energy tensor of electromagnetic field $b_{kl\mu\nu}$). *The 4-index D dimensional stress-energy tensor of electromagnetic field $b_{kl\mu\nu}$ is defined as:*

$$\begin{aligned} b_{kl\mu\nu} &\equiv \left(\left(\frac{R}{D} \right) - a - c - d \right) \times g_{kl\mu\nu} \\ &\equiv (E - a) \times g_{kl\mu\nu} \\ &\equiv b \times g_{kl\mu\nu} \end{aligned} \quad (95)$$

¹L. P. Hughston and K. P. Tod. An introduction to general relativity. Cambridge University Press, Cambridge ; New York, 1990. ISBN 978-0-521-32705-3.

Definition 2.41 (The n-index D dimensional stress-energy tensor of electromagnetic field $b_{kl\mu\nu\dots}$). The n-index D dimensional stress-energy tensor of electromagnetic field $b_{kl\mu\nu\dots}$ is defined as:

$$\begin{aligned} b_{kl\mu\nu\dots} &\equiv \left(\left(\frac{R}{D} \right) - a - c - d \right) \times g_{kl\mu\nu\dots} \\ &\equiv (E - a) \times g_{kl\mu\nu\dots} \\ &\equiv b \times g_{kl\mu\nu\dots} \end{aligned} \quad (96)$$

Definition 2.42 (The tensor $c_{\mu\nu}$). Under conditions of Einstein's general (Einstein, 1915, 1916, 1917, 1935; Einstein and Sitter, 1932) theory of relativity, the tensor of non-momentum and curvature is defined/derived/determined (Barukčić, 2020) as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} c_{\mu\nu} &\equiv b_{\mu\nu} - (\Lambda \times g_{\mu\nu}) \\ &\equiv (G - a) \times g_{\mu\nu} \\ &\equiv \left(\frac{R}{2} - \Lambda - d \right) \times g_{\mu\nu} \\ &\equiv (b - \Lambda) \times g_{\mu\nu} \\ &\equiv c \times g_{\mu\nu} \end{aligned} \quad (97)$$

Definition 2.43 (The 4-index D dimensional tensor $c_{kl\mu\nu}$). The 4-index D dimensional $c_{kl\mu\nu}$ is defined as:

$$\begin{aligned} c_{kl\mu\nu} &\equiv (G - a) \times g_{kl\mu\nu} \\ &\equiv \left(\frac{R}{2} - \Lambda - d \right) \times g_{kl\mu\nu} \\ &\equiv (b - \Lambda) \times g_{kl\mu\nu} \\ &\equiv c \times g_{kl\mu\nu} \end{aligned} \quad (98)$$

Definition 2.44 (The n-index D dimensional tensor $c_{kl\mu\nu\dots}$). The n-index D dimensional $c_{kl\mu\nu\dots}$ is defined as:

$$\begin{aligned} c_{kl\mu\nu\dots} &\equiv (G - a) \times g_{kl\mu\nu\dots} \\ &\equiv \left(\frac{R}{2} - \Lambda - d \right) \times g_{kl\mu\nu\dots} \\ &\equiv (b - \Lambda) \times g_{kl\mu\nu\dots} \\ &\equiv c \times g_{kl\mu\nu\dots} \end{aligned} \quad (99)$$

Definition 2.45 (The tensor of neither curvature nor momentum $d_{\mu\nu}$). Under conditions of Einstein's general (Einstein, 1915, 1916, 1917, 1935; Einstein and Sitter, 1932) theory of relativity, the tensor of neither curvature nor momentum is defined/derived/determined (Barukčić, 2020) as follows:

$$\begin{aligned}
d_{\mu\nu} &\equiv \left(\left(\frac{R}{2} \right) \times g_{\mu\nu} \right) - b_{\mu\nu} \\
&\equiv \left(\left(\frac{R}{2} \right) \times g_{\mu\nu} \right) - (\Lambda \times g_{\mu\nu}) - c_{\mu\nu} \\
&\equiv \left(\frac{\left(\left(\frac{R}{D} \right) \times D \right)}{2} - b \right) \times g_{\mu\nu} \\
&\equiv \left(\frac{\left(\left(\frac{R}{D} \right) \times D \right)}{2} - \Lambda - c \right) \times g_{\mu\nu} \\
&\equiv \frac{R}{D} \times {}_{gw}g_{\mu\nu} \\
&\equiv d \times g_{\mu\nu}
\end{aligned} \tag{100}$$

There may exist circumstances where this tensor might indicate something like the density of gravitational waves. In detail, it is

$$d_{\mu\nu} \equiv \frac{R}{D} \times {}_{gw}g_{\mu\nu} \equiv \left(\left(\frac{R}{2} \right) \times g_{\mu\nu} \right) - \left(\frac{1}{4 \times \pi} \times \left((F_{\mu c} \times F_{\nu d} \times g^{cd}) + \left(\frac{1}{4} \times g_{\mu\nu} \times F_{de} \times F^{de} \right) \right) \right) \tag{101}$$

Under these circumstances, the metric tensor of the gravitational waves ${}_{gw}g_{\mu\nu}$ would follow as

$${}_d g_{\mu\nu} \equiv {}_{gw}g_{\mu\nu} \equiv \frac{D}{R} \times \left(\left(\left(\frac{R}{2} \right) \times g_{\mu\nu} \right) - \left(\frac{1}{4 \times \pi} \times \left((F_{\mu c} \times F_{\nu d} \times g^{cd}) + \left(\frac{1}{4} \times g_{\mu\nu} \times F_{de} \times F^{de} \right) \right) \right) \right) \tag{102}$$

The cosmic microwave background (CMBR) radiation (*Penzias and Wilson, 1965*) is an electromagnetic radiation which is part of the tensor $b_{\mu\nu}$.

Definition 2.46 (The 4-index D dimensional $d_{kl\mu\nu}$). The 4-index D dimensional $d_{kl\mu\nu}$ is defined as:

$$\begin{aligned}
d_{kl\mu\nu} &\equiv \left(\frac{\left(\left(\frac{R}{D} \right) \times D \right)}{2} - b \right) \times g_{kl\mu\nu} \\
&\equiv \left(\frac{\left(\left(\frac{R}{D} \right) \times D \right)}{2} - \Lambda - c \right) \times g_{kl\mu\nu} \\
&\equiv d \times g_{kl\mu\nu}
\end{aligned} \tag{103}$$

Definition 2.47 (The n-index D dimensional $d_{kl\mu\nu\dots}$). The n-index D dimensional $d_{kl\mu\nu\dots}$ is defined

as:

$$\begin{aligned}
 d_{kl\mu\nu\dots} &\equiv \left(\frac{\left(\left(\frac{R}{D} \right) \times D \right)}{2} - b \right) \times g_{kl\mu\nu\dots} \\
 &\equiv \left(\frac{\left(\left(\frac{R}{D} \right) \times D \right)}{2} - \Lambda - c \right) \times g_{kl\mu\nu\dots} \\
 &\equiv d \times g_{kl\mu\nu\dots}
 \end{aligned}
 \tag{104}$$

2.5. Methods

Definitions

Speed of the light in vacuum

Let c denote the speed of light in a vacuum. The exact value of the speed of light in vacuum is defined by the International System of Units (SI) as

$$c = 299,792,458 \text{ m/s} \quad (105)$$

or approximately as

$$c = 3 \times 10^8 \text{ m/s} \quad (106)$$

The wavelength of the light in vacuum

In physics, specifically in the context of waves, λ_R (lambda) represents the wavelength of a wave. For light waves, which travel at a speed c (the speed of light), the wavelength λ_R is related to the frequency f_R of the wave through the equation:

$$\lambda_R = \frac{c}{f_R} = \frac{2\pi}{k_R} \quad (107)$$

where:

- λ_R (lambda) is the wavelength as given from the point of view of a stationary of relativistic observer,
- c is the speed of light in a vacuum (approximately 3×10^8 meters per second),
- f_R is the frequency of the light wave as given from the point of view of a stationary of relativistic observer.

The relationship shows that as the frequency f_R increases, the wavelength λ_R decreases, and vice versa. This is because the speed of light c remains constant. In general, the angular wave number k_R (i.e., the magnitude of the wave vector) is given by:

$$k_R = \frac{2\pi}{\lambda_R} = \frac{2\pi f_R}{v_p} = \frac{\omega_R}{v_p} \quad (108)$$

where:

- f_R is the frequency of the wave,
- λ_R is the wavelength,
- $\omega_R = 2\pi f_R$ is the angular frequency of the wave,
- v_p is the phase velocity of the wave.

The dependence of the wavenumber k on the frequency ν (or more commonly, the frequency on the wavenumber k) is known as a dispersion relation.

The frequency of the light in vacuum

Let f_R denote the frequency of light from the viewpoint of a stationary observer R:

$$f_R = \text{frequency} \quad (109)$$

The reciprocal of the frequency f_R is the period T_R :

$$T_R = \frac{1}{f_R} \quad (110)$$

The reciprocal of the frequency f_R , denoted as $\frac{1}{f_R}$, represents the period T_R of a wave or oscillation. The period T_R is the amount of time it takes for one complete cycle of the wave to occur and is highly deterministic. In other words, if you measure the time interval between two successive peaks (or any other equivalent points) of the wave, you obtain the period T_R .

Mathematically, the relationship is expressed as $T_R = \frac{1}{f_R}$. This indicates that the period and the frequency are inversely related: as the frequency of the wave increases, the period decreases, and vice versa. For example, if a wave has a frequency of 2 Hz (meaning two cycles per second), its period would be $T_R = \frac{1}{2}$ seconds, or 0.5 seconds per cycle.

Understanding the reciprocal relationship between frequency and period (see [Halliday et al., 2013](#)) is fundamental in the study of wave phenomena, whether in physics, engineering, or other scientific disciplines. It applies to various types of waves, including sound waves, light waves, and electromagnetic waves. This concept is crucial for analyzing wave behavior, signal processing, and many other applications where wave properties are important.

In practical terms, knowing the period of a wave helps in determining the timing characteristics of oscillatory systems, such as in electronic circuits, mechanical vibrations, acoustic systems et cetera. This reciprocal relationship is a cornerstone of wave theory and is essential for both theoretical analysis and practical applications.

The position of the light in vacuum

In general, when we multiply velocity v by time t_R , we obtain the displacement x_R of an object. Displacement refers to the distance an object has traveled in a specific direction over a given period of time. The relationship can be expressed as:

$$x_R = v \times t_R \quad (111)$$

Here:

- x_R represents the displacement of the object.
- v is the velocity of the object, which is the rate at which the object changes its position.
- t_R is the time over which the motion occurs within the frame of reference of a relativistic or stationary observer.

In this context, velocity is a vector quantity, meaning it has both magnitude and direction. Therefore, the resulting displacement x_R will also be a vector, indicating both how far and in which direction the object has moved.

For example, if an object moves with a constant velocity of 5 m/s for 10 s, the displacement can be calculated as:

$$x_R = 5 \text{ m/s} \times 10 \text{ s} = 50 \text{ m} \quad (112)$$

This means the object has traveled 50 meters in the direction of the velocity vector over the 10 second period.

Let us multiply the speed of light c by time t_R , we obtain the distance x_R that light travels in that time or the position, where the photons are. The speed of light c is a constant value, approximately 3×10^8 m/s. The relationship can be expressed as:

$$x_R = c \times t_R \quad (113)$$

Here:

- x_R represents the distance that light has traveled or the position, where the photons are located from the point of view of a stationary observer.
- c is the speed of light, which is approximately 3×10^8 m/s.

- t_R is the time over which the light has been traveling as seen from the point of view of a stationary observer.

This equation shows that the distance traveled by light is directly proportional to the time of travel.

For example, if light travels for 2 s, the distance can be calculated as:

$$d = 3 \times 10^8 \text{ m/s} \times 2 \text{ s} = 6 \times 10^8 \text{ m} \quad (114)$$

This means the light has traveled 600,000,000 meters (or 600,000 kilometers) in 2 seconds.

The time t_R measured by a stationary observer and the period of time, defined as (see equation 107, p. 41)

$$T_R = \frac{1}{f_R} = \frac{\lambda_R}{c} \quad (115)$$

are related but represent different concepts in physics.

1. **Time t_R :** This is the time interval measured by a stationary observer R . It can represent any duration of time, such as the time it takes for an event to occur or the time between two events.

2. **Reciprocal of Frequency $T_R = \frac{1}{f_R}$:** The period of time T_R does not represent any duration of time but exactly the time which it takes for one complete cycle of a periodic event, such as a wave or oscillation. If f_R is the frequency of the wave as measured by the stationary observer R , then $\frac{1}{f_R}$ is the period of the wave. In other words, one difference is that t_R is a general relativistic time interval that can refer to any event or duration, while $\frac{1}{f_R}$ specifically refers to the period of a periodic event. Even if both are not the same, both, t_R and $T_R = \frac{1}{f_R}$ measure time itself. Therefore, in general, it is (see equation 115, p. 44)

$$x_R = c \times T_R = \lambda_R \quad (116)$$

and under certain circumstances (see equation 108, p. 41)

$$x_R = c \times T_R = \lambda_R = \frac{2\pi}{k} \quad (117)$$

Planck's Constant h

Planck's constant (see [Planck, 1901](#)) h signifies the quantization of energy levels in atomic and subatomic systems, meaning that energy can only be gained or lost in discrete amounts or quanta.

The exact value of Planck's constant h as fixed by the International System of Units (SI) in 2019 as:

$$h = 6.62607015 \times 10^{-34} \text{ Js} \quad (118)$$

Energy of a photon

Planck's constant h relates the energy of a photon to the frequency of its associated electromagnetic wave. The relationship is given by the equation:

$$E_R = h \times f_R \quad (119)$$

where:

- E_R is the energy of the photon as found by the stationary or relativistic observer R,
- h is Planck's constant,
- f_R is the frequency of the photon as found by the stationary or relativistic observer R.

The generally covariant form of Planck-Einstein relation

Multiplying equation 119 by the metric tensor $g_{\mu\nu}$, it should be given that

$$E_{\mu\nu} = E_R \times g_{\mu\nu} = h \times f_R \times g_{\mu\nu} = h \times f_{\mu\nu} \quad (120)$$

What sense does such a mathematical manoeuvre make, does it have any practical significance at all? In our understanding, it is

$$E_{\mu\nu} = E_R \times g_{\mu\nu} = \left(\frac{4 \times 2 \times \pi \times \gamma}{c^4} \right) \times T_{\mu\nu} = \left(\frac{4 \times 2 \times \pi \times \gamma \times T}{c^4 \times D} \right) \times g_{\mu\nu} = h \times f_R \times g_{\mu\nu} \quad (121)$$

where the scalar E_R of the stress energy tensor of matter $T_{\mu\nu}$ is given (see [Barukčić, 2022](#)) as $E_R = \left(\frac{4 \times 2 \times \pi \times \gamma \times T}{c^4 \times D} \right)$ while D is the space-time dimension and T is Laue's scalar. Under these assumptions, the stress-energy tensor of the frequency $f_{\mu\nu}$ of matter would be given something like

$$f_{\mu\nu} = \frac{E_{\mu\nu}}{h} = \left(\frac{4 \times 2 \times \pi \times \gamma \times T}{c^4 \times D \times h} \right) \times g_{\mu\nu} = \left(\frac{4 \times \gamma \times T}{c^4 \times D \times \hbar} \right) \times g_{\mu\nu} \quad (122)$$

which would additionally enable us to geometrize electromagnetism completely. Planck's constant $h = 2 \times \pi \times \hbar$ itself is determined by a fundamental constant known as the reduced Planck constant or Dirac's constant (see also [Dirac, 1947](#), p. 87), denoted by $\hbar$. Therefore, it is

$$\frac{1}{\hbar} = \frac{2\pi}{h} \quad (123)$$

where h is the Planck constant.

The momentum of a photon

For photons (particles of light), the momentum p_R is related to the frequency f and the speed of light c by:

$$p_R = \frac{h \times f_R}{c} \quad (124)$$

where h is Planck's constant.

According to Einstein's theory of special relativity, it is

$$m_R \times \sqrt{1 - \frac{v^2}{c^2}} = m_0 \quad (125)$$

and (see [Einstein, 1905](#))

$$E_R \times \sqrt{1 - \frac{v^2}{c^2}} = c^2 \times m_R \times \sqrt{1 - \frac{v^2}{c^2}} = c^2 \times m_0 = E_0 \quad (126)$$

where:

- E_R is the relativistic or total energy, the energy as given in the frame of reference of a stationary or relativistic observer R,
- m_R is the relativistic mass (see also [Tolman, 1912](#)), the mass as given in the frame of reference of a stationary or relativistic observer R,
- E_0 is the Energy as given in the frame of reference of a co-moving observer 0,
- m_0 is the rest mass, the mass as given in the frame of reference of a co-moving observer 0,
- c is the speed of light in a vacuum (approximately 3×10^8 meters per second),
- v is the relative velocity between the observers.

Multiply equation (125) by the relative velocity v , we get:

$$p_R \times \sqrt{1 - \frac{v^2}{c^2}} = m_R \times v \times \sqrt{1 - \frac{v^2}{c^2}} = m_0 \times v = p_0 \quad (127)$$

where:

- p_R is the relativistic momentum (see also [Planck, 1906](#)), the momentum as given in the frame of reference of a relativistic observer R,
- p_0 is the momentum as given in the frame of reference of a co-moving observer 0.

In equation (127), the relativistic momentum p_R is related to the relativistic mass m_R , the relative velocity v , and the speed of light c .

The de Broglie relation

Louis Victor Pierre Raymond de Duc de Broglie (1892 - 1987) introduced the de Broglie relation (see [de Broglie, 1924](#)) as a fundamental relationship in quantum mechanics which relates the wavelength of a particle to its momentum. Proposed by Louis de Broglie in 1924, it suggests that all matter exhibits wave-like properties (see [Davisson and Germer, 1928](#)). The de Broglie wavelength λ_R of a particle and its momentum p_R are related by the equation:

$$\lambda_R \times p_R = h \quad (128)$$

where h is Planck's constant and p_R is the momentum of the particle. Dividing equation 128 by 4π it is

$$\left(\frac{\lambda_R}{4\pi}\right) \times p_R = \frac{h}{4\pi} = \frac{\hbar}{2} \quad (129)$$

Under circumstances (see equation 108, p. 41) where

$$\lambda_R = \frac{2\pi}{k} \quad (130)$$

it is possible (see equation 117, p. 44) that the position x_R is given as

$$x_R = c \times T_R = \lambda_R = \frac{2\pi}{k} \quad (131)$$

In other words, a particle should be considered as positioned within its own wavelength. This approach seems logical, as a particle and its wave appear inherently (see [Barukčić, 2013](#)) linked. However, if the particle's associated wave were to exist independently of the particle, even at the edge of our world, fundamental questions could arise on the scientific horizon and lead to significant logical contradictions. Following Heisenberg's understanding of the relationship between position and momentum, we must accept circumstances where the relationship between position x_R and momentum p_R is given (see equation 129) as

$$x_R \times p_R = \left(\frac{2\pi}{k}\right) \times p_R = \frac{h}{4 \times \pi} \quad (132)$$

The rigorous validation and examination of Equation 132 remain areas for future investigation. Nevertheless, regardless of how it is approached, there is no logical space for uncertainties or ambiguities. The equation's logical consistency demands thorough scrutiny to affirm its accuracy and applicability. It stands resilient against any potential doubts or unknowns, embodying a robust framework awaiting comprehensive confirmation through continued study. Clarifying its implications and verifying its assertions will illuminate its role in advancing understanding within its field. Thus, while exploration persists, the equation's foundational integrity remains unwavering, poised for deeper exploration into its implications and significance.

3. Results

3.1. Energy, Time and Newton's Law of Gravitation

Theorem 1. *Newton's law of gravitation describes the relationship between energy and time.*

Proof. We start with the fundamental equation:

$$1 = 1 \quad (133)$$

We multiply the previous equation by the relativistic masses m_{1R} and m_{2R} . We obtain:

$$m_{1R} \times m_{2R} = m_{1R} \times m_{2R} \quad (134)$$

We then divide the previous equation by the relativistic distance d_R between the two masses, yielding:

$$\frac{m_{1R} \times m_{2R}}{d_R^2} = \frac{m_{1R} \times m_{2R}}{d_R^2} \quad (135)$$

Next, we multiply this equation by the Newtonian constant G_R and get:

$$G_R \times \frac{m_{1R} \times m_{2R}}{d_R^2} = G_R \times \frac{m_{1R} \times m_{2R}}{d_R^2} \quad (136)$$

Newton's law of gravitation is thus given by:

$$F_R = G_R \times \frac{m_{1R} \times m_{2R}}{d_R^2} \quad (137)$$

According to Einstein's mass-energy equivalence, we have $m_{1R} = \frac{E_{1R}}{c^2}$ and $m_{2R} = \frac{E_{2R}}{c^2}$. Substituting these relations into Equation 137, we get:

$$F_R = G_R \times \frac{\left(\frac{E_{1R}}{c^2}\right) \times \left(\frac{E_{2R}}{c^2}\right)}{d_R^2} \quad (138)$$

The distance between the masses is measured by the relativistic time t_R , which is the time light takes to travel between the two masses. Thus, $d_R = c \times t_R$. Substituting this into the previous equation changes it to:

$$F_R = G_R \times \frac{\left(\frac{E_{1R}}{c^2}\right) \times \left(\frac{E_{2R}}{c^2}\right)}{(c \times t_R)^2} \quad (139)$$

Newton's law of gravitation essentially expresses a relationship between energy and time in the form:

$$F_R = \left(\frac{G_R}{c^2 \times c^2 \times c^2}\right) \times \left(\frac{E_{1R} \times E_{2R}}{t_R^2}\right) \quad (140)$$

To simplify, we define

$$\beta = \left(\frac{G_R}{c^2 \times c^2 \times c^2}\right) \quad (141)$$

which is approximately:

$$\beta = \left(\frac{G_R}{c^2 \times c^2 \times c^2}\right) = \left(\frac{6.67430 \times 10^{-11}}{(2.99792458 \times 10^8)^2 \times (2.99792458 \times 10^8)^2 \times (2.99792458 \times 10^8)^2}\right) = 9.19351324 \times 10^{-62} \quad (142)$$

In general, the relationship between energy and time, due to Newton, is given as

$$F_R = \beta \times \left(\frac{E_{1R} \times E_{2R}}{t_R^2}\right) \quad (143)$$

This equation can be further refined. Under conditions where the relation $E_R = h \times f_R$ holds, with f_R representing the relativistic frequency, we obtain:

$$F_R = \left(\frac{h^2 \times G_R}{c^2 \times c^2 \times c^2}\right) \times \left(\frac{f_{1R} \times f_{2R}}{t_R^2}\right) \quad (144)$$

where h is the Planck constant. The Planck constant h has a value of approximately:

$$h \approx 6.62607015 \times 10^{-34} \text{ Js} \quad (145)$$

Squaring this value yields:

$$h^2 \approx (6.62607015 \times 10^{-34} \text{ Js})^2 \approx 4.135667696 \times 10^{-67} \text{ J}^2 \text{ s}^2 \quad (146)$$

In terms of SI units, this can also be expressed as:

$$h^2 \approx 4.135667696 \times 10^{-67} \text{ kg}^2 \text{ m}^4 \text{ s}^{-4} \quad (147)$$

where J stands for joules, m for meters, kg for kilograms, and s for seconds. As light travels towards an observer from a source that is receding, its wavelength becomes elongated, causing a shift toward the red end of the spectrum, known as redshift. This redshift serves as a valuable indicator of how far the light-emitting source has moved away from the observer since the emission of the light. By measuring this shift, scientists can gauge the distance and velocity of the object, offering insights into the dynamics of cosmic changes. In point of fact, in cosmology, measurements are often made using the wavelength of light, λ_{1R} and λ_{2R} due to the known relationship $c = \lambda_{2R} \times f_{2R}$. In general, it is $f = \frac{c}{\lambda}$. We obtain

$$F_R = \left(\frac{h^2 \times G_R}{c^2 \times c^2 \times c^2} \right) \times \left(\frac{c^2}{t_R^2 \times \lambda_{1R} \times \lambda_{2R}} \right) = \left(\frac{h^2 \times G_R}{c^2 \times c^2} \right) \times \left(\frac{1}{\lambda_{1R} \times \lambda_{2R} \times t_R^2} \right) \quad (148)$$

or in more simpler terms:

$$F_R = \left(\frac{h^2 \times G_R}{c^2} \right) \times \left(\frac{1}{\lambda_{1R} \times \lambda_{2R} \times d_R^2} \right) \quad (149)$$

□

It is

$$\left(\frac{h^2 \times G_R}{c^2} \right) = \left(\frac{4.135667696 \times 10^{-67} \times (2.99792458 \times 10^8)^2 \times 6.67430 \times 10^{-11}}{(2.99792458 \times 10^8)^2} \right) = 3.07121311 \times 10^{-94} \quad (150)$$

Example

In cosmology, the wavelength of light from hydrogen is often measured in the context of its spectral lines. One of the most significant wavelengths associated with hydrogen is the Lyman-alpha line, which corresponds to a transition from the $n = 2$ to the $n = 1$ energy level in the hydrogen atom. The Lyman-alpha line of hydrogen has a rest wavelength of approximately:

$$\lambda_0 = 1216 \text{ \AA} \text{ (angstroms)} = 1216 \times 0.1 \frac{\text{nm}}{\text{\AA}} = 121.6 \text{ nm} \quad (151)$$

The wavelength of 121.6 nm is equivalent to 1.216×10^{-7} meters. In the context of science, when observing phenomena, the observed wavelength, λ_{obs} , will be redshifted or blueshifted. This relationship is given by:

$$\lambda_{\text{obs}} = \lambda_0(1 + z) \quad (152)$$

where z is the redshift.

Hypothetical example: Observations of a galaxy by the James Webb Space Telescope

Let us assume, the James Webb Space Telescope has observed a galaxy with a redshift of $z = 14.32$ (see also Carniani et al., 2024). The rest wavelength of the Lyman-alpha line of hydrogen is $\lambda_0 = 121.6$ nm. The distances and properties are of course to some extent uncertain.

Gravitational force

The observed wavelength λ_{obs} can be calculated using the formula:

$$\lambda_{\text{obs}} = \lambda_0(1 + z) \quad (153)$$

Substituting the values:

$$\lambda_{\text{obs}} = 121.6 \text{ nm} \times (1 + 14.32) = 121.6 \text{ nm} \times 15.32 \approx 1867.552 \text{ nm} \quad (154)$$

Given wavelength:

$$\lambda = 1867.552 \text{ nm} \quad (155)$$

To convert the wavelength from nanometers (nm) to meters (m), use the conversion factor:

$$1 \text{ nm} = 10^{-9} \text{ m} \quad (156)$$

The wavelength in meters is calculated as:

$$\lambda = 1867.552 \text{ nm} \times 10^{-9} \frac{\text{m}}{\text{nm}} = 1.867552 \times 10^{-6} \text{ m} \quad (157)$$

Distance Calculation

To estimate the distance d of a galaxy with a redshift $z = 14.32$, we use the following cosmological distance formula.

$$d \approx \frac{c \times z}{H_0} \quad (158)$$

where:

- $c = 3 \times 10^5$ km/s (speed of light),
- $H_0 = 70$ km/s/Mpc (Hubble constant),
- $z = 14.32$ (redshift).

Substituting the values:

$$d \approx \frac{3 \times 10^5 \text{ km/s} \times 14.32}{70 \text{ km/s/Mpc}} \approx 6120 \text{ Mpc} \quad (159)$$

Converting the distance to meters:

$$d \approx 6120 \text{ Mpc} \times 3.09 \times 10^{22} \text{ m/Mpc} \approx 1.89 \times 10^{26} \text{ meters} \quad (160)$$

To convert this distance to seconds (light-travel time), use:

$$\text{Distance in seconds} = \frac{d}{c} = \frac{1.89 \times 10^{26} \text{ meters}}{3 \times 10^8 \text{ m/s}} \approx 6.3 \times 10^{17} \text{ seconds} \quad (161)$$

Assuming 1 year $\approx 3.154 \times 10^7$ seconds. The distance to a galaxy with a redshift of $z = 14.32$ is approximately:

- 2.00×10^{10} light-years.

or approximately in billions of light-years:

$$\text{Distance in billions of light-years} = \frac{2.00 \times 10^{10} \text{ light-years}}{10^9} = 20 \text{ billion light-years} \quad (162)$$

In other words, the distance to the galaxy would be approximately:

- 20 billion light-years.

In order to calculate the Newton's force due to gravitation, it is:

$$F_R = \left(\frac{h^2 \times G_R}{c^2} \right) \times \left(\frac{1}{\lambda_0 \times \lambda_{obs} \times d_R^2} \right) \quad (163)$$

or

$$F_R = \left(\frac{4.135667696 \times 10^{-67} \times 6.67430 \times 10^{-11}}{(2.99792458 \times 10^8)^2} \right) \times \left(\frac{1}{1.216 \times 10^{-7} \times 1.867552 \times 10^{-6} \times (1.89 \times 10^{26})^2} \right) = 3.78599527 \times 10^{-134} \quad (164)$$

These calculations are purely hypothetical. It is almost certain that our Earth did not exist over 20 billion light years ago.

3.2. Proof: Laue's scalar T

Laue's Scalar T in general

Laue's scalar T is a quantity used in the context of relativity and stress-energy tensors to represent the trace or the invariant magnitude of the energy-momentum tensor $T_{\mu\nu}$. Laue's scalar T provides something like a measure of the total energy (density and pressure) of a system in a relativistic framework.

Theorem. The stress energy tensor of matter $T_{\mu\nu}$ and Laue's Scalar T

Theorem 2 (Laue's Scalar and the stress energy tensor of matter). *In general, Laue's Scalar T is a determining part of the Einstein's field equation as:*

$$T = T^\mu{}_\mu = g^{\mu\nu}T_{\mu\nu} \quad (165)$$

Proof by direct proof. We begin this proof by acknowledging the identity:

$$1 = 1 \quad (166)$$

Multiplying equation 166 by $T_{\mu\nu}$, we obtain

$$T_{\mu\nu} = T_{\mu\nu} \quad (167)$$

As next we take the trace of the energy-momentum tensor $T_{\mu\nu}$. The trace of the energy-momentum tensor is given by the contraction

$$g^{\mu\nu}T_{\mu\nu} = g^{\mu\nu}T_{\mu\nu} \quad (168)$$

where $g^{\mu\nu}$ is the inverse metric tensor. This scalar invariant provides a simplified characterization of the energy-momentum tensor by summing the contributions of energy density and isotropic pressures in the system. Equation 168 is equivalent with

$$T = T^\mu{}_\mu = g^{\mu\nu}T_{\mu\nu} \quad (169)$$

which completes our proof. $\square$

Meaning and Context of Laue's Scalar

Laue's scalar T captures how energy density affects gravitational interactions, highlighting the interplay between mass-energy content and the geometry of space-time, a fundamental principle of general relativity.

1. **Energy-Momentum Tensor:** In general relativity, the energy-momentum tensor $T_{\mu\nu}$ is a symmetric tensor that describes the distribution and flow of energy and momentum in spacetime. It encapsulates not only energy density but also momentum density and stresses (pressure and shear).
2. **Trace T of the Energy-Momentum Tensor of Matter:** The trace T of the energy-momentum tensor given by a contraction as:

$$T = T^\mu{}_\mu = g^{\mu\nu}T_{\mu\nu} \quad (170)$$

can provide insights into the physical characteristics of the matter or field distribution.

3. For electromagnetic fields in a vacuum, it is possible that the trace is zero ($T = 0$), reflecting the fact that electromagnetic radiation is traceless.
4. **Role in scalar Theories of Gravity:** Laue's scalar is of principal use in scalar theories of gravity or cosmology, where modifications to the energy-momentum tensor play a role in defining new gravitational dynamics.

Laue's scalar T provides a concise summary of the energy-momentum distribution's properties in a given spacetime. It is particularly useful in theoretical physics, where understanding the invariant properties of matter and energy is essential for formulating and solving equations of motion in relativistic contexts.

3.3. Proof: Scalar foundation of the Einstein's field equations

In general, the Einstein field equations (EFE) as a set of ten interrelated differential equations in the general theory of relativity describe how matter and energy interact with the curvature of spacetime, which we perceive as gravity. These equations are expressed in a generally covariant form, meaning they hold true regardless of the coordinate system used. Thus far, is it possible at all to find something like a scalar foundation of the Einstein's field equations? The mathematical reduction of the Einstein's field equations to something like scalars would theoretically mean transforming a set of complex tensor equations into a single scalar equation. Such a simplification could make calculations involving gravitational fields significantly easier, especially in complex scenarios involving multiple interacting masses but can be associated with problems too.

Theorem 3. *In general, the scalar foundation of the Einstein's field equations is given as:*

$$\left(\left(\frac{R}{D}\right) - \left(\left(\frac{R}{2}\right) - (\Lambda)\right)\right) = \left(\left(\frac{8 \times \pi \times G}{c^4 \times D}\right) \times T\right) \quad (171)$$

Proof. We start with the fundamental equation:

$$1 = 1 \quad (172)$$

As next, we multiply the previous equation by the stress-energy tensor $\left(\left(\frac{8 \times \pi \times G}{c^4}\right) \times T_{\mu\nu}\right)$ in order to obtain:

$$\left(\left(\frac{8 \times \pi \times G}{c^4}\right) \times T_{\mu\nu}\right) = \left(\left(\frac{8 \times \pi \times G}{c^4}\right) \times T_{\mu\nu}\right) \quad (173)$$

According to Einstein's general relativity, we have to consider the equivalence of

$$\left(G_{\mu\nu} + (\Lambda \times g_{\mu\nu})\right) = \left(\left(\frac{8 \times \pi \times G}{c^4}\right) \times T_{\mu\nu}\right) \quad (174)$$

Rearranging equation 174, we get

$$\left(R_{\mu\nu} - \left(\frac{R}{2} \times g_{\mu\nu}\right) + (\Lambda \times g_{\mu\nu})\right) = \left(\left(\frac{8 \times \pi \times G}{c^4}\right) \times T_{\mu\nu}\right) \quad (175)$$

Taking the trace of the Einstein's field equations, it is

$$\left(R_{\mu\nu} - \left(\frac{R}{2} \times g_{\mu\nu}\right) + (\Lambda \times g_{\mu\nu})\right) \times g^{\mu\nu} = \left(\left(\frac{8 \times \pi \times G}{c^4}\right) \times T_{\mu\nu}\right) \times g^{\mu\nu} \quad (176)$$

It is $g_{\mu\nu} \times g^{\mu\nu} = D$. The Einstein's field equations can be reduced to scalars given as

$$\left(R - \left(\frac{R \times D}{2}\right) + (\Lambda \times D)\right) = \left(\left(\frac{8 \times \pi \times G}{c^4}\right) \times T\right) \quad (177)$$

Equation 177 is highlighting the interplay between mass-energy content and the geometry of space-time, a fundamental principle of general relativity. Dividing equation 177 by the spacetime dimension $D = g_{\mu\nu} \times g^{\mu\nu}$, we obtain the scalar foundation of the Einstein's field equations as

$$\left(\left(\frac{R}{D}\right) - \left(\left(\frac{R}{2}\right) - (\Lambda)\right)\right) = \left(\left(\frac{8 \times \pi \times G}{c^4 \times D}\right) \times T\right) \quad (178)$$

where:

- **G - Newton's Gravitational Constant:**

- G is the constant of proportionality in Newton's law of universal gravitation. It describes the strength of gravity in the framework of classical mechanics.

- **c - Speed of Light:**

- c is the speed of light in a vacuum, a fundamental constant in physics representing the maximum speed at which information or matter can travel.

- **D - Space-Time Dimension:**

- D represents the number of dimensions in the space-time model being considered. In general relativity, D is typically 4 (3 spatial dimensions and 1 time dimension), but higher dimensions can be considered in various theoretical physics contexts.

- **T - Laue's Scalar:**

- Laue's scalar, T , refers to a scalar quantity related to the stress-energy tensor, often representing energy density or pressure in relativistic contexts.

□

Some consequences

Based on equation 178, we obtain

$$\frac{\left(\left(\frac{R}{D}\right) - \left(\left(\frac{R}{2}\right) - (\Lambda)\right)\right)}{\left(\left(\frac{8 \times \pi \times G}{c^4 \times D}\right) \times T\right)} = \frac{\left(\left(\frac{R}{D}\right) - \left(\left(\frac{R}{2}\right) - (\Lambda)\right)\right) \times c^4 \times D}{8 \times \pi \times G \times T} = 1 \quad (179)$$

What does general relativity tell us about conditions where $T = 0$ and the mathematical validity of equation 179? Must we accept that $0 / 0 = 1$? Furthermore, Newtons constant G_R is determined as

$$G_R = \frac{\left(\left(\frac{R}{D}\right) - \left(\left(\frac{R}{2}\right) - (\Lambda)\right)\right) \times c^4 \times D}{(8 \times \pi \times T)} = \frac{\left(\left(\frac{R}{D}\right) - \left(\left(\frac{R}{2}\right) - (\Lambda)\right)\right) \times c^4 \times g_{\mu\nu} g^{\mu\nu}}{(8 \times \pi \times T)} = \frac{\left(\left(G_{\mu\nu}\right) + (\Lambda \times g_{\mu\nu})\right) \times c^4 \times g^{\mu\nu}}{(8 \times \pi \times T)} = \text{constant?} \quad (180)$$

Treating Newton's constant G_R as a constant could exclude manifolds where $(G_{\mu\nu} + (\Lambda \times g_{\mu\nu})) = 0$ or where $G_{\mu\nu} = -(\Lambda \times g_{\mu\nu})$. Furthermore, Newton's constant G_R treated as constant, might yield to problems where Laue's scalar $T = 0$. In general, the term $\frac{8\pi G}{c^4} \frac{T}{D}$ in the scalar form of the Einstein field equations represents something like a normalized form of the stress-energy tensor $T_{\mu\nu}$, where T is its trace, scaled by constants that relate gravitational effects to matter and energy. In General Relativity, $\frac{8\pi G}{c^4} T_{\mu\nu}$ quantifies the contribution of matter and energy to the curvature of spacetime. However, the term $\frac{8\pi G}{c^4} \frac{T}{D}$ is a specific scaled version that takes into account the number of spacetime dimensions D too. This term need not directly correspond to the total energy in quantum mechanics or relativistic energy E_R , though it provides a scaled view of how energy and momentum are related in the context of spacetime curvature. In general, tensors can encapsulate directionality and relationships in multiple dimensions, while a scalar under normal circumstances provides a single value at each point in space. Therefore, even if the term $\left(\left(\frac{8\pi \times G}{c^4 \times D}\right) \times T\right)$ is likely to represent something like a contribution to the curvature of space-time from energy or matter described by Laue's scalar T , the danger is great that a scalar equation could provide less information than the full tensor form of the equations. In other words, various of the nuances of how gravity operates could be lost. Such and similar arguments are important but ultimately unconvincing. Briefly, it is important to emphasise that the spacetime dimension D is a part of equation 178. By reducing the Einstein's field equations to a scalar form, the generally covariant nature of general relativity could be compromised but need not. Indeed, the beauty of general relativity is its ability to describe physical laws that are the same in every coordinate system and many times, the full tensor form of the Einstein field equations is essential for capturing the complex and rich phenomena of objective reality. A scalar form of the Einstein's field equations should not destroy this feature. In particular, reducing the Einstein field equations to a scalar form would represent a significant simplification of general relativity theory, potentially making certain calculations easier. However, this should not happen at the cost of losing critical information and predictive power of general relativity. There are circumstances where the scalar form of the Einstein's field equation as derived by equation 178 might provide an accessible framework for understanding certain gravitational phenomena. Nonetheless, there are circumstances too, where the depth and general applicability of the full tensorial Einstein field equations as

$$\left(\left(\frac{R}{D}\right) - \left(\left(\frac{R}{2}\right) - (\Lambda)\right)\right) \times g_{\mu\nu\dots} = \left(\left(\frac{8 \times \pi \times G}{c^4 \times D}\right) \times T\right) \times g_{\mu\nu\dots} \quad (181)$$

is justified too.

Theorem. The speed of light in vacuum

Theorem 4 (Speed of the light in vacuum). *In general, based on equation 178, it is*

$$c^2 = \left(\left(\frac{8 \times \pi \times G}{\left(\left(\frac{R}{D}\right) - \left(\left(\frac{R}{2}\right) - (\Lambda)\right)\right) \times c^2 \times D}\right) \times T\right) \quad (182)$$

Proof by direct proof. In general, it is (see equation 178)

$$E = \left(\left(\frac{R}{D} \right) - \left(\left(\frac{R}{2} \right) - (\Lambda) \right) \right) = \left(\left(\frac{8 \times \pi \times G}{c^4 \times D} \right) \times T \right) \quad (183)$$

The term E should not be mismatched with relativistic energy E_R . Furthermore, we continue by acknowledging the identity:

$$1 = 1 \quad (184)$$

In other words, it is

$$\left(\left(\frac{R}{D} \right) - \left(\left(\frac{R}{2} \right) - (\Lambda) \right) \right) = \left(\left(\frac{R}{D} \right) - \left(\left(\frac{R}{2} \right) - (\Lambda) \right) \right) \quad (185)$$

or

$$\left(\left(\frac{R}{D} \right) - \left(\left(\frac{R}{2} \right) - (\Lambda) \right) \right) = \left(\left(\frac{8 \times \pi \times G}{c^4 \times D} \right) \times T \right) \quad (186)$$

The speed of the light in vacuum is determined as

$$c^2 = \left(\left(\frac{8 \times \pi \times G}{\left(\left(\frac{R}{D} \right) - \left(\left(\frac{R}{2} \right) - (\Lambda) \right) \right) \times c^2 \times D} \right) \times T \right) \quad (187)$$

□

Theorem. Energy E_R and mass m_R are determining the speed of light in vacuum

Theorem 5 (Speed of the light in vacuum). *In general, it is*

$$c^2 = \frac{E_R}{m_R} \quad (188)$$

Proof by direct proof. We begin by acknowledging the identity:

$$1 = 1 \quad (189)$$

and

$$E_R = E_R = c^2 \times m_R \quad (190)$$

In general, it is

$$c^2 = \frac{E_R}{m_R} \quad (191)$$

□

3.4. Proof: Relativistic mass and the Einstein's field equations

Theorem 6. In general, the relativistic mass m_R can be derived from the Einstein's field equation as:

$$m_R = \frac{E_R \times \left(\left(\frac{R}{D} \right) - \left(\left(\frac{R}{2} \right) - (\Lambda) \right) \right) \times c^2 \times D}{8 \times \pi \times G \times T} = \left(\frac{c^2}{8 \times \pi \times G} \right) \times \left(\frac{D \times E_R}{T} \right) \times \left(\left(\frac{R}{D} \right) - \left(\left(\frac{R}{2} \right) - (\Lambda) \right) \right) \quad (192)$$

Proof. We begin by acknowledging the identity:

$$1 = 1 \quad (193)$$

Under circumstances where various observer agree on the speed of the light in vacuum, the relationship

$$c = c \quad (194)$$

is given. It follows that

$$c^2 = c^2 \quad (195)$$

Thus, equating the two expressions for c^2 (see equation 187 and equation 191), we get:

$$\frac{E_R}{m_R} = \left(\left(\frac{8 \times \pi \times G}{\left(\left(\frac{R}{D} \right) - \left(\left(\frac{R}{2} \right) - (\Lambda) \right) \right) \times c^2 \times D} \right) \right) \times T \quad (196)$$

As next, we multiplying both sides of equation 196 by m_R , we arrive at the relativistic energy E_R as:

$$E_R = \left(\left(\frac{8 \times \pi \times G}{\left(\left(\frac{R}{D} \right) - \left(\left(\frac{R}{2} \right) - (\Lambda) \right) \right) \times c^2 \times D} \right) \right) \times T \times m_R \quad (197)$$

The relativistic mass m_R , i. e. for further use in Newton's law of gravitation, can be calculated from the Einstein's field equation as:

$$m_R = \frac{E_R \times \left(\left(\frac{R}{D} \right) - \left(\left(\frac{R}{2} \right) - (\Lambda) \right) \right) \times c^2 \times D}{8 \times \pi \times G \times T} \quad (198)$$

This completes the proof under the given conditions.

□

Equation 198 need to be adjusted to account for particular conditions. Laue's scalar T itself is given by the equation

$$T = \frac{\left(\left(\frac{R}{D}\right) - \left(\left(\frac{R}{2}\right) - (\Lambda)\right)\right) \times c^2 \times D}{8 \times \pi \times G \times m_R} \times E_R \quad (199)$$

$$T = \left(\frac{\left(\left(\frac{R}{D}\right) - \left(\left(\frac{R}{2}\right) - (\Lambda)\right)\right) \times c^2 \times D}{8 \times \pi \times G \times m_R}\right) \times E_R = \text{something} \times E_R \quad (200)$$

and can be interpreted as proportional to E_R . However, only under conditions where

$$\text{something} = \left(\frac{\left(\left(\frac{R}{D}\right) - \left(\left(\frac{R}{2}\right) - (\Lambda)\right)\right) \times c^2 \times D}{8 \times \pi \times G \times m_R}\right) = 1 \quad (201)$$

Laue's scalar T and relativistic energy E_R are identical, but not in general. In brief, it is

$$m_R = \frac{m_0}{\sqrt{1 - \left(\frac{v}{c}\right)^2}} = \frac{E_R \times \left(\left(\frac{R}{D}\right) - \left(\left(\frac{R}{2}\right) - (\Lambda)\right)\right) \times c^2 \times D}{8 \times \pi \times G \times T} \quad (202)$$

The rest mass of a particle m_0 or another entity according to Einstein's general theory of relativity should be given as

$$m_0 = \sqrt{1 - \left(\frac{v}{c}\right)^2} \times \frac{E_R \times c^2 \times D}{8 \times \pi \times G \times T} \times \left(\left(\frac{R}{D}\right) - \left(\left(\frac{R}{2}\right) - (\Lambda)\right)\right) \quad (203)$$

Multiplying equation 203 by the metric tensor $g_{\mu\nu}$ it is

$${}_0M_{\mu\nu} = m_0 \times g_{\mu\nu} = \sqrt{1 - \left(\frac{v}{c}\right)^2} \times \frac{E_R \times c^2 \times D}{8 \times \pi \times G \times T} \times \left(\left(\frac{R}{D}\right) - \left(\left(\frac{R}{2}\right) - (\Lambda)\right)\right) \times g_{\mu\nu} \quad (204)$$

or

$${}_0M_{\mu\nu} = \sqrt{1 - \left(\frac{v}{c}\right)^2} \times \frac{E_R \times c^2 \times D}{8 \times \pi \times G \times T} \times (G_{\mu\nu} + (\Lambda \times g_{\mu\nu})) \quad (205)$$

where ${}_0M_{\mu\nu}$ it the stress tensor of rest mass. Exotic matter with negative energy density, often considered in hypothetical scenarios such as wormholes and warp drives, presents intriguing possibilities. However, Einstein's field equations in General Relativity impose stringent constraints that these negative energy configurations may violate, particularly concerning energy conditions. The necessity for positive energy density to maintain stable and physically viable solutions suggests that negative matter remains largely infeasible within our current understanding of objective reality. Nevertheless, based on the Einstein's field equations, negative matter should be determined as

$$-m_0 = -\left(\sqrt{1 - \left(\frac{v}{c}\right)^2} \times \frac{E_R \times c^2 \times D}{8 \times \pi \times G \times T} \times \left(\left(\frac{R}{D}\right) - \left(\left(\frac{R}{2}\right) - (\Lambda)\right)\right)\right) \quad (206)$$

3.5. Proof: Newton's law of gravitation and general covariance

Theorem 7. In general, Newton's law of gravitation is determined by general covariance as

$$F_{\mu\nu} = \left(\frac{D \times c^4}{8 \times \pi \times T} \right) \times \left(\frac{m_{1R} \times m_{2R}}{d_R^2} \right) \times (G_{\mu\nu}) + (\Lambda \times g_{\mu\nu}) \quad (207)$$

Proof by direct proof. Initial Identity

The proof begins with the acknowledgment of a fundamental identity:

$$1 = 1 \quad (208)$$

This equation is a simple tautology used as a starting point to establish equivalence in mathematical derivations. It sets the foundation for comparing or transforming expressions under this truth.

Newton's Law of Gravitation

Next, we state that:

$$F_R = F_R \quad (209)$$

This identity restates Newton's law of gravitation for consistency:

$$F_R = G_R \times \frac{m_{1R} \times m_{2R}}{d_R^2} \quad (210)$$

This equation defines F_R as the gravitational force between two masses m_{1R} and m_{2R} , separated by a distance d_R , with G_R being the gravitational constant in the relativistic context.

The gravitational constant G_R is expressed as:

$$G_R = \frac{\left(\left(\frac{R}{D} \right) - \left(\left(\frac{R}{2} \right) - (\Lambda) \right) \right) \times c^4 \times D}{8 \times \pi \times T} = \frac{\left(\left(\frac{R}{D} \right) - \left(\left(\frac{R}{2} \right) - (\Lambda) \right) \right) \times c^4 \times g_{\mu\nu} g^{\mu\nu}}{8 \times \pi \times T} = \frac{\left((G_{\mu\nu}) + (\Lambda \times g_{\mu\nu}) \right) \times c^4 \times g^{\mu\nu}}{8 \times \pi \times T} \quad (211)$$

In this step, G_R is related to the Einstein tensor $G_{\mu\nu}$, the cosmological constant Λ , and the metric tensor $g_{\mu\nu}$, reflecting the relationship between general relativity and gravitation. Substituting the expression for G_R (see equation 211) into equation 210, we obtain:

$$F_R = \left(\frac{\left(\left(\frac{R}{D} \right) - \left(\left(\frac{R}{2} \right) - (\Lambda) \right) \right) \times c^4 \times D}{8 \times \pi \times T} \right) \times \left(\frac{m_{1R} \times m_{2R}}{d_R^2} \right) \quad (212)$$

Equation 212 integrates components of the Einstein's relativistic field equations into Newton's law of gravitation. We rearrange equation 212 and multiply the rearranged equation by the metric tensor $g_{\mu\nu}$ of general relativity to obtain:

$$F_R \times g_{\mu\nu} = \left(\frac{c^4 \times D}{8 \times \pi \times T} \right) \times \left(\frac{m_{1R} \times m_{2R}}{d_R^2} \right) \times \left(\left(\frac{R}{D} \right) - \left(\left(\frac{R}{2} \right) - (\Lambda) \right) \right) \times g_{\mu\nu} \quad (213)$$

Typically, F_R would denote a force, which is usually a vector. In the context of equation 213, F_R represent a scalar quantity like the magnitude of a force. Multiplying a scalar by a tensor $g_{\mu\nu}$ does not change the rank of the tensor. Considering circumstances where

$$F_{\mu\nu} = F_R \times g_{\mu\nu} \quad (214)$$

we do obtain

$$F_{\mu\nu} = \left(\frac{D \times c^4}{8 \times \pi \times T} \right) \times \left(\frac{m_{1R} \times m_{2R}}{d_R^2} \right) \times (G_{\mu\nu}) + (\Lambda \times g_{\mu\nu}) \quad (215)$$

Rewriting equation 215 in terms of energy and time, under circumstances where $d_R = c \times t_R$, we have:

$$F_{\mu\nu} = \left(\frac{1}{8 \times \pi} \right) \times \left(\frac{c^2 \times m_{1R} \times c^2 \times m_{2R}}{c^2 \times t_R^2} \right) \times \left(\frac{D}{T} \right) \times (G_{\mu\nu} + (\Lambda \times g_{\mu\nu})) \quad (216)$$

This reformulation emphasizes the interplay between mass, energy, and the spacetime metric, illustrating how Newton's law of gravitation can be understood in terms of gravitational interactions, energy density and spacetime geometry. Rearranging equation 216, we derive the generally covariant form of Newton's law of gravitation as:

$$F_{\mu\nu} = \left(\frac{1}{4 \times 2 \times \pi \times c^2} \right) \times \left(\frac{E_{1R} \times E_{2R}}{t_R^2} \right) \times \left(\frac{D}{T} \right) \times (G_{\mu\nu} + (\Lambda \times g_{\mu\nu})) \quad (217)$$

This formulation is more concise and highlights the interrelation between energy, time, and gravitational interactions within the framework of general relativity. We then incorporate quantum mechanics into Equation 217, emphasizing how fundamental constants can link classical and quantum physics. This approach also paves the way for exploring quantum gravity by demonstrating how these constants bridge the gap between classical theories and quantum considerations within the context of general relativity. We then utilize the relationship $h = 2 \times \pi \times \hbar$ and its inverse $\frac{1}{2 \times \pi} = \frac{\hbar}{h}$ to simplify equation 217. This process reveals a streamlined form of the equation, reflecting the deep, contradiction free connection between these fundamental physical theories, general relativity and quantum mechanics.

$$F_{\mu\nu} = \left(\frac{\hbar}{4 \times h \times \pi \times c^2} \right) \times \left(\frac{E_{1R} \times E_{2R}}{t_R^2} \right) \times \left(\frac{D}{T} \right) \times \left(G_{\mu\nu} + (\Lambda \times g_{\mu\nu}) \right) \quad (218)$$

At this occasion, we consider circumstances where $E_{1R} = h \times f_{1R}$ and where $E_{2R} = h \times f_{2R}$. Equation 218 simplifies under these circumstances as

$$F_{\mu\nu} = \left(\frac{h \times h \times \hbar}{4 \times h \times \pi \times c^2} \right) \times \left(\frac{f_{1R} \times f_{2R}}{t_R^2} \right) \times \left(\frac{D}{T} \right) \times \left(G_{\mu\nu} + (\Lambda \times g_{\mu\nu}) \right) \quad (219)$$

or as

$$F_{\mu\nu} = \left(\frac{h \times \hbar}{4 \times \pi \times c^2} \right) \times \left(\frac{f_{1R} \times f_{2R}}{t_R^2} \right) \times \left(\frac{D}{T} \right) \times \left(G_{\mu\nu} + (\Lambda \times g_{\mu\nu}) \right) \quad (220)$$

It is $h = 2 \times \pi \times \hbar$ and $\frac{h}{\pi} = 2 \times \hbar$. Equation 217 simplifies further as:

$$F_{\mu\nu} = \left(\frac{2 \times \hbar \times \hbar}{4 \times c^2} \right) \times \left(\frac{f_{1R} \times f_{2R}}{t_R^2} \right) \times \left(\frac{D}{T} \right) \times \left(G_{\mu\nu} + (\Lambda \times g_{\mu\nu}) \right) \quad (221)$$

Equation 221 is rearranged as

$$F_{\mu\nu} = \left(\frac{1}{2} \right) \times \left(\frac{\hbar}{c} \right)^2 \times \left(\frac{f_{1R} \times f_{2R}}{t_R^2} \right) \times \left(\frac{D}{T} \right) \times \left(G_{\mu\nu} + (\Lambda \times g_{\mu\nu}) \right) \quad (222)$$

It is $c = f \times \lambda$ and $f = \frac{c}{\lambda}$. Equation 222 is particularly relevant for cosmological observations too and becomes:

$$F_{\mu\nu} = \left(\frac{\hbar^2}{2} \right) \times \left(\frac{1}{\lambda_{1R} \times \lambda_{2R} \times t_R^2} \right) \times \left(\frac{D}{T} \right) \times \left(G_{\mu\nu} + (\Lambda \times g_{\mu\nu}) \right) \quad (223)$$

□

In general, there are circumstances where the term

$$\left(\left(\frac{\hbar^2}{2} \right) \times \left(\frac{1}{\lambda_{1R} \times \lambda_{2R} \times t_R^2} \right) \times \left(\frac{D}{T} \right) \right) \quad (224)$$

can be treated as a scalar f . In other words, Newton's law of gravitation can be expressed in a simpler way as follows:

$$F_{\mu\nu} = f \times \left(G_{\mu\nu} + (\Lambda \times g_{\mu\nu}) \right) \quad (225)$$

3.6. Proof: Wormholes

What are Wormholes? Wormholes (see also [Einstein and Rosen, 1935](#)) are hypothetical tunnels (see also [Wheeler, 1957](#)) in spacetime that could connect distant regions of the universe. They arise as solutions to the equations of General Relativity, typically requiring exotic matter with negative energy density to remain stable. First proposed by [Einstein and Rosen \(1935\)](#) and further developed by [Wheeler \(1957\)](#), these concepts arise from solutions to the equations of General Relativity. Although purely hypothetical, wormholes are intriguing because they could theoretically allow for faster-than-light travel between distant regions of the universe. However, keeping wormholes stable typically requires exotic matter with negative energy density, posing significant theoretical challenges.

Wormhole Metric

The metric for a traversable wormhole, as described by Morris and Thorne, is given by:

$$ds^2 = -c^2 dt^2 + \frac{dr^2}{1 - \frac{b(r)}{r}} + r^2(d\theta^2 + \sin^2 \theta d\phi^2) \quad (226)$$

where:

- ds^2 is the spacetime interval.
- c is the speed of light.
- t is the time coordinate.
- r, θ, ϕ are the spherical coordinates.
- $b(r)$ is the shape function, which determines the wormhole's geometry. It must satisfy the condition $b(r_0) = r_0$, where r_0 is the throat of the wormhole.

For the wormhole to be traversable, the following conditions must hold:

1. **No Event Horizon:** The function $1 - \frac{b(r)}{r}$ must be greater than zero for all $r > r_0$.
2. **Flare-Out Condition:** At the throat $r = r_0$, the derivative $b'(r_0) < 1$ to ensure the wormhole's stability.
3. **Exotic Matter:** The matter threading the wormhole must violate the null energy condition, meaning $\rho + p_r < 0$, where ρ is the energy density and p_r is the radial pressure.

The metric tensor for a traversable wormhole, as described by Morris and Thorne, can be represented by:

$$g_{\mu\nu} = \begin{bmatrix} -c^2 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \frac{1}{1-\frac{b(r)}{r}} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & r^2 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & r^2 \sin^2 \theta \end{bmatrix} \quad (227)$$

where each element of the tensor corresponds to the components of the spacetime metric:

- $g_{00} = -c^2$ represents the time component.
- $g_{11} = \frac{1}{1-\frac{b(r)}{r}}$ represents the radial component.
- $g_{22} = r^2$ corresponds to the polar angular component.
- $g_{33} = r^2 \sin^2 \theta$ corresponds to the azimuthal angular component.

The metric tensor $g_{\mu\nu}$ describes the geometry of spacetime, where:

- g_{00} is associated with the time component and represents the gravitational time dilation.
- g_{11} is the radial component, which includes the shape function $b(r)$ that determines the wormhole's geometry.
- g_{22} and g_{33} are the angular components describing the spherical symmetry of the wormhole.

Theorem. F_R and Wormholes

Theorem 8 (Gravitation and wormholes). *Newton's law of gravitation applied to wormholes gives:*

$$F_{\mu\nu} = \left(\frac{D \times E_{1R} \times E_{2R}}{8 \times \pi \times c^2 \times T \times t_R^2} \right) \times \left((G_{\mu\nu}) + (\Lambda \times g_{\mu\nu}) \right) = (scalar\ f) \times \left((G_{\mu\nu}) + (\Lambda \times g_{\mu\nu}) \right) \quad (228)$$

Proof by direct proof. We begin by acknowledging the identity:

$$1 = 1 \quad (229)$$

which lead us to the equation

$$F_R = F_R \quad (230)$$

and finally to the statement of Newton's law of gravitation expressed as:

$$F_R = G_R \times \frac{m_{1R} \times m_{2R}}{d_R^2} \quad (231)$$

where F_R is the gravitational force, G_R is Newton's gravitational 'constant', m_1R and m_2R are the masses, and d_R^2 is the distance between the centers of the two masses. Newton's gravitational constant G_R is determined by the Einstein tensor $G_{\mu\nu}$, the cosmological constant Λ , and the metric tensor $g_{\mu\nu}$ et cetera, reflecting the dynamics of changes within objective reality. According to equation 211, it is

$$G_R = \left(\frac{\left(\left(\frac{R}{D} \right) - \left(\left(\frac{R}{2} \right) - (\Lambda) \right) \right) \times c^4 \times D}{8 \times \pi \times T} \right) = \frac{\left(\left(\frac{R}{D} \right) - \left(\left(\frac{R}{2} \right) - (\Lambda) \right) \right) \times c^4 \times g_{\mu\nu} g^{\mu\nu}}{8 \times \pi \times T} = \frac{\left((G_{\mu\nu}) + (\Lambda \times g_{\mu\nu}) \right) \times c^4 \times g^{\mu\nu}}{8 \times \pi \times T} \quad (232)$$

Substituting the result of equation 232 into equation 231, we do obtain:

$$F_R = \left(\frac{\left(\left(\frac{R}{D} \right) - \left(\left(\frac{R}{2} \right) - (\Lambda) \right) \right) \times c^4 \times D}{8 \times \pi \times T} \right) \times \frac{m_{1R} \times m_{2R}}{d_R^2} \quad (233)$$

Multiplying equation 233 by the metric tensor for a traversable wormhole $g_{\mu\nu}$, as described by Morris and Thorne, we obtain

$$F_R \times g_{\mu\nu} = \left(\frac{\left(\left(\frac{R}{D} \right) - \left(\left(\frac{R}{2} \right) - (\Lambda) \right) \right) \times c^4 \times D}{8 \times \pi \times T} \right) \times \frac{m_{1R} \times m_{2R}}{d_R^2} \times g_{\mu\nu} \quad (234)$$

Equation 234 can be rearranged as

$$F_{\mu\nu} = F_R \times g_{\mu\nu} = \left(\frac{D \times c^4 \times m_{1R} \times m_{2R}}{8 \times \pi \times T \times d_R^2} \right) \times \left(\left(\frac{R}{D} \right) - \left(\left(\frac{R}{2} \right) - (\Lambda) \right) \right) \times g_{\mu\nu} \quad (235)$$

and simplified to

$$F_{\mu\nu} = \left(\frac{D \times E_{1R} \times E_{2R}}{8 \times \pi \times c^2 \times T \times t_R^2} \right) \times \left((G_{\mu\nu}) + (\Lambda \times g_{\mu\nu}) \right) = (\text{scalar } f) \times \left((G_{\mu\nu}) + (\Lambda \times g_{\mu\nu}) \right) \quad (236)$$

□

Theoretically wormholes offer potential shortcuts through spacetime, offering insights into the fundamental structure of spacetime and the possibilities of faster travel. In other words, the study of wormholes is very important. Nonetheless, wormholes arise as solutions to the equations of General Relativity, but their stability appears to require exotic matter, which challenges our current understanding of physics. Developing more realistic and appropriate tools like equation 236, which can be simplified further, is essential for accurately modeling these phenomena and exploring their feasibility within the framework of both classical, relativity and quantum physics. Improved theoretical models can help address key questions about wormhole stability, traversability, and their role in the broader context of spacetime topology and quantum gravity. As such, advancing our theoretical toolkit is vital for expanding our understanding of the universe and potentially unlocking new technological and scientific frontiers.

4. Discussion

In theoretical physics, expressing Newton's law of gravitation in a generally covariant form could imply a significant shift in how gravitational interactions are understood and described, particularly in relation to the concept of wormholes and the fabric of spacetime.

General Covariance and Gravitation

General Covariance: General covariance is a principle stating that the laws of physics should take the same form in all coordinate systems. It is a cornerstone of Einstein's theory of General Relativity, which describes gravity not as a force but as a curvature of spacetime caused by mass and energy.

Newton's Law in Covariant Form: In classical mechanics, Newton's law of gravitation is expressed as:

$$F_R = G_R \times \frac{m_{1R} \times m_{2R}}{d_R^2} \quad (237)$$

where F_R is the gravitational force, G_R is the gravitational constant, m_{1R} and m_{2R} are the masses, and d_R^2 is the distance between the centers of the two masses. A generally covariant form would require expressing this law in terms of tensors that are invariant under general coordinate transformations. This would involve replacing the scalar gravitational potential with a metric tensor $g_{\mu\nu}$, which describes the geometry of spacetime.

Impact of Covariant Formulation

Unified Description

Adopting a generally covariant approach to Newtonian gravity could harmonize the description of gravitational phenomena with the geometric interpretation of gravity, offering a coherent framework for exploring concepts such as wormholes.

Spacetime Topology

Adapting Newton's law of gravity to a generally covariant form would imply that classical gravity might both influence and be influenced by changes in spacetime topology, including those hypothesized for wormholes.

Quantum Gravity Insights

This reformulation could shed light on quantum gravity by bridging the gap between classical and relativistic descriptions. It may enhance our understanding of wormholes, particularly in the context of quantum gravity and quantum tunneling.

Stability and Traversability

Analyzing wormhole stability within a generally covariant Newtonian framework could establish new criteria for their traversability and stability, potentially eliminating the need for exotic matter. This would address a significant challenge in theoretical studies.

Energy Conditions

This framework could redefine the energy conditions necessary for wormholes, offering fresh insights into how classical energy conditions are either satisfied or violated. Understanding these conditions is crucial for assessing the feasibility of wormholes.

Why Explore Covariant Formulation?

Incorporating the principles of General Relativity into Newtonian gravity through a covariant formulation could merge classical physics with a geometric view of gravity. This approach has the potential to reveal new insights into the behavior and characteristics of various theoretical constructs including wormholes.

Unified Approach

Creating a generally covariant version of Newtonian gravity could align the study of gravitational phenomena with the geometric framework of General Relativity. This unified perspective would provide a consistent foundation for exploring intricate structures even of quantum gravity.

Impact on Spacetime Topology

Reformulating Newton's law of gravity in a covariant manner implies that classical gravity might interact with or be affected by changes in spacetime topology too. This could help bridge the gap between classical and relativistic understandings of gravity.

Insights into Quantum Gravity

A covariant reinterpretation of Newtonian gravity might offer valuable insights into quantum gravity, facilitating a reconciliation between classical and relativistic theories. Examining gravity in this new context could provide fresh perspectives on the foundations of quantum gravity, quantum tunneling and quantum computers.

Stability and Traversability

The hope is strong and well-founded that investigating wormhole stability within a covariant Newtonian framework could establish new criteria for their traversability and stability, potentially eliminating any theoretical need for any kind of exotic matter. This could overcome a significant obstacle in theoretical studies, making wormholes a more feasible concept and of more practical relevance.

Redefining Energy Conditions

This approach could redefine the energy conditions necessary for wormholes, offering new insights into how classical energy conditions are satisfied or violated. Understanding these conditions could turn out to be vital for evaluating the practicality of wormholes.

Nevertheless, despite the ongoing debates and complexities, expressing Newton's law in a covariant form presents several key challenges that need to be addressed too.

Mathematical Complexity.

Formulating a covariant version that aligns with both Newtonian mechanics and General Relativity involves intricate mathematical structures. This approach may require addressing too much complex issues related to singularities and infinities.

Experimental Verification.

The predictions of such a covariant formulation must be subject to empirical testing. This is especially crucial in contexts involving strong gravitational fields or on cosmological scales.

Consistency with Observations.

It is imperative to underscore with utmost clarity that the new formulation must be in complete agreement with well-established gravitational phenomena, such as planetary orbits and gravitational waves, which are precisely described by General Relativity.

5. Conclusion

Exploring a generally covariant form of Newton's law of gravitation holds the promise of advancing our understanding of gravitational phenomena and spacetime. While the theoretical implications for wormholes are intriguing, they also present substantial challenges that require further investigation. This endeavor underscores the ongoing efforts to integrate classical and relativistic gravity theories, potentially paving the way for new discoveries in gravitational physics and cosmology.

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Erratum

Unfortunately, some misprints appeared in the previous publications, especially in the section of definitions. Some of the misprints have been brought up to date in this publication as far as possible.

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